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Abstract:

This report summarizes the events in the SSHOC stakeholder series. This series comprises ten events that took place between May 2019 and July 2021. The list includes workshops, debates, and conferences. The events reached a total of 1283 participants across all SSHOC stakeholder categories.

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Executive Summary

The SSHOC stakeholder series aimed to showcase the progress and achievements of the projects and engage with a wider range of SSHOC stakeholders and other European initiatives; to promote the uptake of SSHOC tools, services, and shared data, equip producers, users, and experts with relevant skills and capabilities, and support the collaboration with other initiatives. The events in the series were designed to be cross-stakeholder to maximise the outreach and to foster the dialog and collaboration between SSHOC stakeholders.

The central event of the series was the mid-project stakeholder forum. Organised in collaboration with EOSC-hub¹ and FREYA² projects, the forum took place in October 2020 as the *Realising European Open Science Cloud* conference. Motivated by the post-event review of the SSHOC stakeholder categories, a plan for the organisation of a series of further events was established, with the aim of reaching all stakeholder categories.

The ten events in the stakeholder series are:

1. Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud: What's in it for research libraries? (Workshop at LIBER2019 conference), 26 June 2019
2. Language as social and cultural data (talk at the "Culture & Technology" European Summer University in Digital Humanities), 2 August 2019
3. EOSC services, collaborations, and RDA (co-located event at 14th RDA Plenary), 21 October 2019
4. Social & Cultural Data – taking the Users' Perspective (session at the EOSC Symposium 2019), 28 November 2019
5. Realising the European Open Science Cloud: Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond, 16-19 November 2020
6. SSH Code of Conduct Workshop, 17 March 2021
7. The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons (debate co-located with RDA's 17th Virtual Plenary Meeting)
8. Round Table of Experts on Data Citation, 20 May 2021
9. Onboarding Citizen Science and the role of research libraries: barriers and accelerators (workshop at the LIBER2021 Conference), 23 June 2021
10. SSH Vocabulary Initiative - What users want (workshop at the ICTeSSH 2021 Conference), 28 June 2021

The events in the series range from large conferences to sessions or workshops organised as part of other events attended by specific stakeholder groups or scientific communities. The largest event was

¹ EOSC-hub has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 777536, <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>, accessed on 8 October 2021.

² The FREYA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 777523, <https://www.project-freya.eu/>, accessed on 8 October 2021.

the *Realising European Open Science Cloud* conference with an exhibition, networking opportunities, 29 sessions and over 110 speakers and session chairs. In total, the events reached 1283 people.

The stakeholder series highlighted the impact of the project activities and developments, placing them in the broader context of European technical and social developments in the social sciences and humanities and EOSC. The events are a major contribution to the promotion of SSHOC project achievements and to the engagement with stakeholders.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICTeSSH	ICT Enhanced Social Sciences and Humanities
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
MCSQ	Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Science & Humanities Open Cloud
WP	Work package

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1. Introduction

This report concerns the events of the SSHOC stakeholder series that showcased the progress and achievements of the project and provided opportunity for the project Consortium to engage with a wider range of SSHOC stakeholders and a variety of European initiatives. The organisation followed the objectives of SSHOC Work Package 6 to promote the uptake of SSHOC tools, services, and shared data, focusing on the FAIR principles, empowering data producers, users, and experts with relevant skills and capabilities, and supporting collaboration with other initiatives. The events in the series were designed to be cross-stakeholder in order to maximise the outreach and foster the dialog and collaboration among SSHOC stakeholders.

Figure 1: SSHOC stakeholders

Source: Torma et al., 2019

The series was based on the principles defined in the *Deliverable 6.1 Community Engagement Strategy* (Torma et al., 2019) and described in more detail in *Report on Milestone 39: Launch Expertise Strategy* (Vipavc Brvar et al., 2020). The SSHOC stakeholder groups were defined in the *Deliverable 2.1 SSHOC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan* (Schwabe et al., 2019).

This report begins with an outline of the methodology of the organisation process, followed by a summarized list of the events. The final section provides an overview of the outcomes. Full reports on respective events are annexed at the end.

2. Organisation of the Events

Stakeholder series began with several events in 2019 and 2020 that had provided an insight into the expected impact of the SSHOC innovations for specific stakeholder groups. The event series then evolved further from the central event – the mid-project stakeholder forum, originally designed as a cross-stakeholder, face-to-face event organised in collaboration with the other ESFRI thematic clusters³ and co-located with a larger event. The goal of the stakeholder forum was to engage with a broader range of SSHOC stakeholders and other European initiatives to showcase the project progress and achievements, ensure that all stakeholder groups were represented, and gather 100-200 participants. With the organisation of the event underway in early 2020,⁴ the format and programme of the forum were significantly impacted by the epidemic and the limited resources of the other cluster projects. Finally organised in cooperation with the EOSC-hub and FREYA projects, the forum took place in October 2020 as the *Realising European Open Science Cloud* conference.⁵ The event was very well attended, provided a wide range of activities and included different ways of approaching the era of online conferencing during the pandemic. A post-event review was also organised, to plan the future engagement. Based on the results, and in order to assure ideal outreach and engagement of all SSHOC stakeholder categories (particularly policy makers and research funders) a plan was set in WP6 for a SSHOC Stakeholders series. This prompted the organisation of several new events, which demonstrated the wide thematic scope of the project and had a cross-stakeholder audience.

The events in the series range from large conferences (*Realising European Open Science Cloud* conference) to sessions or workshops organised at other events attended by specific stakeholder or scientific communities (such as the discussion sessions at the Research Data Alliance Plenaries⁶ or the workshop at the ICTeSSH2021 conference⁷). Most of the events were organised in collaboration with SSHOC WP2 (*Communication, Dissemination, and Impact*). Many project partners were involved in the execution of the events, which also included contributions from the representatives of other ESFRI cluster projects and European scientific initiatives.

³ ESFRI thematic cluster projects are: EOSC-Life for biological and medical research, ENVRI-FAIR for Environmental Research Infrastructure, ESCAPE for the area of astronomy- and accelerator-based particle physics, PaNOSC for the area of Photon and Neutron science, and SSHOC for social sciences and humanities.

⁴ Initial planning process and definition of the scope and purpose of the forum are described in Milestone 39 (Vipavc Brvar et al., 2020).

⁵ See sub-chapter 3.5 and Annex 5 for more information.

⁶ See sub-chapter 3.3 and 3.7 as well as Annexes 3 and 7 for more information.

⁷ See sub-chapter 3.9 and Annex 9 for more information.

After the start of the COVID-19 epidemic, all events took place online. Even though the virtual format presented challenges for the organisation, promotion, and interaction with participants, it also provided an opportunity to reach new audiences who were now able to participate without the need to travel. Putting a positive spin on the overload of virtual events in that period, and the appearance of the *Zoom fatigue*, these experiences led to introduction of innovative formats (such as the house-of-commons⁸ styled debate) to keep the interest of the attendants. The most complex event in terms of organisation was the Realising EOSC conference with an exhibition, networking opportunities, 29 sessions and over 110 speakers and session chairs. The conference took place in a virtual events platform VFairs⁹ that gamified the experience and enabled the interaction among the participant and within the (virtual) venue, bringing it closer to attending an in-person conference.

The focus of the series was on the stakeholders. The stakeholder series was an opportunity to bring the progress of the project closer to specific communities. This was achieved by:

- a) identifying the events where community members meet and organising sessions or co-located events for this specific community; and by
- b) focusing on the topics, tools and services that are relevant to those communities and by engaging relevant speakers both from the SSHOC project and from outside the project.

3. Summary of the Events

The stakeholder series comprised a total of **ten events**:

- one major conference,
- four workshops,
- a talk,
- a session at a conference, and
- three discussion panels.

The events reached a total of **1283 people**. The distribution within the stakeholder categories is as follows:

- Uncategorised: 570
- Research and e-infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters: 287
- Research libraries and archives: 162
- Universities and research institutes: 143
- Researchers: 56
- Private sector and industry: 44
- Policy makers: 8
- Civil society and citizen scientists: 8
- Research funders: 5

⁸ In this event, two opposing teams argued in favour or against the three thought-provoking statements provided by the statement makers. The members of the debate team did not present their own opinions but had taken on theatrical roles. See sub-chapter 3.7 for more information.

⁹ VFAIRS event platform. <https://www.vfairs.com/>, accessed on 8 October 2021.

The following sections provide a chronological list of the events with a brief overview of the topic and target audience, as well as the links to published materials.

3.1 Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud: What's in it for research libraries?

Workshop at LIBER2019 conference

Date and venue	26 June 2019, Dublin, Ireland
Topics	SSHOC project, Marketplace and the SSHOC Training Network
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/liber-annual-event-workshop-social-sciences-humanities-open-cloud-what%E2%80%99s-it-research
Main event homepage	https://wayback.archive-it.org/12503/20190730171815/https://liberconference.eu/programme/workshops/social-sciences-humanities-open-cloud/
Presentations	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3364505
Blog post	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/social-sciences-humanities-open-cloud-what%E2%80%99s-it-research-libraries
Audience	
Targeted audience	research libraries and archives (namely research librarians)
Total participants	109
By stakeholder category	Research libraries and archives: 55 Uncategorised: 54
Event report	see <i>Annex 1</i>

3.2 Language as social and cultural data

Lecture at the "Culture & Technology" European Summer University in Digital Humanities

Date and venue	2 August 2019, Bibliotheca Albertina at the University of Leipzig, Germany
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Topics	Contribution of research infrastructures to the emerging paradigms for studying social and cultural dynamics based on language data
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/culture-technology-european-summer-university-digital-humanities
Main event homepage	https://esu.culintec.de/?q=node/1171
Video recording	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3402109
Audience	
Targeted audience	researchers (namely young researchers from the humanities, engineering and information sciences)
Total participants	over 90
Event report	see <i>Annex 2</i>

3.3 EOSC services, collaborations, and RDA

Co-located event at 14th RDA Plenary

Date and venue	21 October 2019, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland
Topics	Commonalities and collaboration of the EOSC cluster projects in community research data management.
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/eosc-services-collaborations-and-rda
Main event homepage	https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rdas-14th-plenary-helsinki-finland
Presentations	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3581075
Blog post	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/eosc-esfri-cluster-projects-rda%C2%A0connecting-commonalities-and-collaborative-solutions-community
Audience	

Targeted audience	researchers, research and e-Infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters (including research data experts and RDA communities, working and interest group members)
Total participants	42
By stakeholder category	Research funders: 1 Research libraries and archives: 6 Research and e-infrastructures and thematic clusters: 22 Private sector and industry: 1 Policy makers: 2 Universities and research performing organisations: 9 Researcher: 1
Event report	see <i>Annex 3</i>

3.4 Social & Cultural Data – taking the Users’ Perspective

Session at the EOSC Symposium 2019

Date and venue	28 November 2019, Danubius Hotel Helia, Budapest, Hungary
Topics	User perspective on requirements regarding certification and trust, training, and sensitive data.
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/eosc-symposium-2019
Main event homepage	https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium
Presentations	https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium2019/social-cultural-data-taking-users%E2%80%99-perspective%20
Proceedings	https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/files/eosc-symposium-2019_report.pdf
Audience	
Targeted audience	research and e-infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters, universities and research institutes, researchers, industry and private sector, civil society and citizen scientists, policy makers, research funders (also EOSC Coalition of Doers, publishers, data service providers)
Total participants	over 32

Event report	see <i>Annex 4</i>
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3.5 Realising the European Open Science Cloud: Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond

Date and venue	16-19 November 2020, online
Topics	Data policy and governance, technology and infrastructure, training and community building, sustainability management ... See event report for details (<i>Annex 5</i>).
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/realising-european-open-science-cloud
Main event homepage	https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud
Presentations	https://zenodo.org/communities/realisingtheeoscevent/?page=1&size=20
Video recordings	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLpuwwe1MpnqKKTezIRIHDaNx_zlo4yuRC
Blog post	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/realising-eosc-virtual-conference-difference
Audience	
Targeted audience	researchers, research funders, policy makers, research and e-infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters, research libraries and archives
Total participants	707
	Research and e-Infrastructures: 257 Universities and research performing organisations: 112 Research libraries and archives: 74 Private sector and industry: 39 Researchers: 48 Civil society and citizen scientists: 8 Policy makers: 6 Research funders: 4 Uncategorised: 159

Event report	see <i>Annex 5</i>
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3.6 SSH Code of Conduct Workshop

Date and venue	17 March 2021, online
Topics	Establishing a Code of Conduct in social sciences and humanities
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-workshop-ssh-code-conduct-0
Presentations	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4655623
Notes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4792297
Blog post	https://sshopencloud.eu/news/workshop-notes-code-conduct-social-sciences-and-humanities
Audience	
Targeted audience	policy makers, universities and research institutes (namely practitioners and others working with GDPR, research ethics, and Codes of Conduct)
Total participants	35
By stakeholder category	Universities and research performing institutions: 14 Researchers: 7 Research libraries and archives: 4 Research and e-infrastructure, EOSC thematic clusters: 3 Uncategorised: 7
Event report	see <i>Annex 6</i>

3.7 The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons

Debate co-located with RDA's 17th Virtual Plenary Meeting

Date and venue	19 April 2021, online
Topics	Commonalities and collaboration in the ESFRI clusters in the context of thematic data services, connecting to end-user communities, and governance

Links to materials	
Announcement	https://sshopencloud.eu/events/esfri-clusters-rda-house-commons
Co-located event homepage	https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-17th-plenary-meeting-co-located-events
Presentation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4723646
Blog post	https://sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-clusters-rda-house-commons-report-out-now
Audience	
Targeted audience	researchers, research and e-infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters (namely members of the international RDA community, the ESFRI community, EOSC ecosystem and data experts and domain researchers)
Total participants	126
Event report	see <i>Annex 7</i>

3.8 Round Table of Experts on Data Citation

Date and venue	20 May 2021
Topics	FAIR SSH citation prototype and Data Citation Recommendation
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://sshopencloud.eu/events/round-table-experts-data-citation
Blog post	https://sshopencloud.eu/news/roundtable-experts-data-citation
Audience	
Targeted audience	research libraries and archives, researchers (namely social science and humanities scholars, experts in data citation)
Total participants	50
Event report	see <i>Annex 8</i>

3.9 Onboarding Citizen Science and the role of research libraries: barriers and accelerators

Workshop at the LIBER2021 Conference

Date and venue	23 June 2021, online
Topics	FAIR research data, multidisciplinary, citizen science
Links to materials	
Announcement	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-liber-2021-conference-onboarding-citizen-science-and-role-research-libraries-barriers
Main event home page	https://liber2021.sched.com/#
Presentations	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5036504
Video recording	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cINWqLgObbg
Blog post	https://sshopencloud.eu/news/onboarding-citizen-science-and-role-research-libraries-barriers-and-accelerators-post-event
Audience	
Targeted audience	research libraries and archives, civil society, and citizen scientists
Total participants	40
By stakeholder category	Research libraries and archives: 23 Universities and research performing organisations: 8 Research and e-infrastructures: 5 Private sector and industry: 4
Event report	see <i>Annex 9</i>

3.10 SSH Vocabulary Initiative - What users want

Workshop at the ICTeSSH 2021 Conference

Date and venue	28 June 2021, online
Topics	Vocabulary initiative, multilingual vocabularies, interoperability, findability

Links to materials	
Announcement	https://sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-vocabulary-initiative-what-users-want%C2%A0ictessh-2021-sshoc-session
Main event home page	https://ictessh.uns.ac.rs/ictessh-2021/
Presentations	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5045017
Video recording	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NShl2fr4Uzs
Event proceedings	https://doi.org/10.21428/7a45813f.ca4aecfc
Audience	
Targeted audience	researchers, private sectors and industry, research libraries and archives, policy makers
Total participants	52
Event report	see <i>Annex 10</i>

4. Outcomes and Conclusions

The stakeholder series was an important contribution to the promotion of SSHOC project achievements and to the engagement with stakeholder communities in social sciences and humanities disciplines. The events in the series were part of the rich portfolio of SSHOC project training, dissemination activities, presentations at attended events, awareness raising and engagement events, and community meetings.¹⁰ The stakeholder series underlined the impact of the project activities and developments and placed them in the broader context of European technical and social developments in the social sciences and humanities and EOSC.

Although the success of the series could be gauged from the substantial total number of participants, the invaluable contribution of numerous speakers and chairs should also be mentioned. Over 150 speakers contributed to the quality of the events and shaped the series by sharing their knowledge, insights, and energy.

The events have all reached the goal of attracting between 30 and 100 participants each. The attendance was monitored as best possible (see Figure 2). The technical limitations of organising co-located events and the lack of overview of the audience mean varied levels of detail on the participants in individual events. Over 40% of the participants remain uncategorised. The best represented categories of the remaining 60% are representatives of research libraries and archives and of research and e-infrastructures. The most difficult groups to reach proved to be policy makers, research funders, and citizen scientists. The first two groups will be targeted in the final conference of the project. For the citizen scientists, the workshop at the LIBER2021 conference¹¹, organised as a focused follow-up to the session¹² in the Realising EOSC conference, was an opportunity to reach them through the liaison with librarians. The overview of the series can confirm that co-locating events with the established community conferences or meetings is a very good strategy for gaining visibility and aligning with the community needs, interests, and updates.

¹⁰ These will be reported on in future deliverables, such as D6.3 *Final report on the outcome of the awareness raising workshops*, D6.4 *Report on awareness webinars*, D6.12 *Report on the Train-the-trainer Bootcamps*, D6.14 *Report of training workshops 1-6* and D6.15 *Report on training webinars 1-6*.

¹¹ See sub-chapter 3.9 and Annex 9.

¹² Session *Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?*. See Annex 5.

Figure 2. Audience by stakeholder category

Three events of the series were organised as face-to-face events. The opportunities and challenges of virtual events would have been met even without the Covid-19 pandemic that had for the large part of the project duration prevented travel and in-person participation. The entire project team was heavily involved in the organisation, technical support, and documentation of online events, as well as in the promotion of visibility of the outputs, even when the events were part of larger events that were organised outside of the project. Technical aspects of online events are to some extent beyond control, with hardware and network difficulties arising even to the most experienced and well-briefed speakers. Due to such disruptions, moderation and technical support was especially challenging and needed to be able to adapt on the fly.

On the other hand, one advantage of online events is that they can easily be recorded and shared. The video recordings, the official proceedings, presentation slides (available in the SSHOC YouTube channel (SSH Open Cloud, n.d.) and Zenodo community (Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud, n.d.)), blogs (published on the project website), and social media response, continue to provide a relevant source on the project achievements for SSHOC stakeholders.

Despite the challenges, the stakeholder series events have succeeded in spreading the message to a large audience. Because they were conducted online, the recordings and materials will remain available for use and impactful for much longer than they would have, had the events been held in person.

5. Reference list

- Torma, M., Kalaitzi, V., Vipavc Brvar, I., Fišer, D., Pahor de Maiti, K., Petitfils, C., Durco, M., Grant, F., & Willems, M. (2019). *SSHOC D6.1 Community Engagement Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592244>
- Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud (n.d.). *Home* [Zenodo community]. Retrieved October 20, 2021, <https://zenodo.org/communities/sshoc/?page=1&size=20>
- SSH Open Cloud (n.d.). *Home* [YouTube channel]. Retrieved October 20, 2021, from <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCw-mY8v84yeHW2z4KG3ZLtA>
- Schwabe, A., Ausserhofer, J., Marino, L., Willems, M., Kalaitzi, V., Vipavc Brvar, I., Smith, E., & Muscella, S. (2019). *SSHOC D2.1 Overall Communication and Outreach Plan (approved 18 Nov 2019)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595936>
- Vipavc Brvar, I., Masten, S., Braukmann, R., Leenarts, E. & Willems, M. (2020). *MS39 Launch expertise strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4585407>

6. List of Annexes

- Annex 1: Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud: What's in it for Research Libraries? Workshop Report
- Annex 2: "Language as social and cultural data" Lecture at the European Summer University in Digital Humanities: Session Report
- Annex 3: EOSC Services, Collaborations and RDA: Event Report
- Annex 4: "Social & Cultural Data – taking the Users' Perspective" session at EOSC Symposium 2019: Session Report
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ANNEX 1

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud: What's in it for research libraries?

Workshop Report

Written by Vasso Kalaitzi and Rosie Allison, LIBER

Background

This report concerns the SSHOC stakeholder engagement event [Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud: What's in it for research libraries?](#), which took place on June 26th 2019, during the LIBER2019 Conference in Dublin. The event was co-organised by [SSHOC](#) and the [LIBER](#) working groups on [Digital Skills for library staff and researchers](#) and on [Digital Humanities and digital cultural heritage](#).

Workshop Overview & Format

The event had the format of a workshop and aimed at establishing first connections with the members of the two LIBER working groups, as well as other interested attendees of the [LIBER2019](#) Conference, which is the Annual meeting event of some 450 representatives of research libraries and other communities around Europe.

The event was attended by 109 LIBER2019 Conference participants. 69 of the present participants actively responded in the interactive session using the Mentimeter tool. 32 of them identified themselves as library management and 19 as librarians. 40 of the participating libraries reported that they cover both Social Sciences and Humanities. Only 14 participants were aware of SSHOC prior to this engagement event.

Presentations & Discussions: Key Points

The introductory presentations were made by Vasso Kalaitzi, LIBER and SSHOC WP6 leader, Cécile Swiatek, co-chair of the LIBER Digital Skills Working Group and Lotte Wilms, co-chair of the Digital Humanities Working Group. During the introductions, a general framework of the SSHOC project was presented, including the planning of upcoming activities towards building expertise for users, and especially libraries, as well as information on the two working groups.

The presentation that followed was provided by Laure Barbot, DARIAH, focusing on the vision, initial stage and upcoming development of the SSH Open Marketplace. DARIAH is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium of 18 member countries and several co-operating partners, with 4 main strategic pillars: Education & Training, Foresight & Policy work, Working groups and Marketplace. Information was provided on the strategic goals on the SSH Open Marketplace, being a discovery

service, with the goal to focus on solutions, workflows, recipes, scenarios and use cases more than tools or services. The process, elements and timeline were presented in detail to the audience, providing several profiles of user stories for better comprehension of the service. The SSH Open Marketplace will be a useful tool for the reinforcement of relationships between librarians and researchers, it will support librarians in easily finding answers to their own training and supporting needs and it will reflect existing, useful resources.

Ellen Leenarts, DANS, presented two main upcoming products related to the SSHOC building expertise activities: the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit and the SSH Training Community. An overview of current training hubs and networks were provided, in order to create a matrix of synergies and commonalities in training. The Train-the-Trainer format that SSHOC uses is very relevant to research libraries, who have a prominent role as trainers within their institutions, towards researchers and other stakeholders, but also in the context of SSHOC and the EOSC. The upcoming SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps and SSH community were presented, urging the audience to follow development and join the SSHOC community of trainers.

The presentations were followed by a focus moment, Q&A, a Mentimeter session and input on behalf of the audience about their needs on skills building and training.

The session was moderated by Darja Fišer, CLARIN. The closing remarks were provided by Bertil F. Dorch, University Library of Southern Denmark. All presentations are available on [Zenodo](#).

Outcomes & Feedback

Following the identification session, the interactive part focussed more on training, with 32 of the Mentimeter participants reporting that they receive requests to find/advise on research datasets and tools monthly, while 17 more reported that they receive such requests weekly. The vast majority of those requests come from researchers, while they are followed by fellow librarians, students, citizen scientists, policymakers, research funders and industry partners.

The discussion expanded to the criteria that should be met in order for research librarians to recommend a tool or a service, including recommendations, user-friendliness, open source nature, existing documentation, data protection and potential price. The audience provided input on their procedure in finding new software and services, the main obstacles in this discovery process, as well as their opinions on how this process could be improved for research libraries and researchers.

How could this discovery process be improved?

More than half of the responding participants reported that their libraries provide regular training to their library staff, while training is also provided to researchers, lecturers, students, and citizen scientists. Regarding training, the discussion also covered available budget, the existence of a training coordinator within the institution, the identification of prominent organisations providing relevant training in their region, as well as their expectations in terms of training events, materials, and services to be provided by SSHOC.

What kind of activities would you like SSHOC to organise to reinforce the SSH training network?

 54

The input collected on behalf of SSHOC by the audience during the event was used in the strategic planning of SSHOC in terms of engagement, building expertise and needs for services and tools.

A [blog post](#) was published after the event.

ANNEX 2

“LANGUAGE AS SOCIAL AND CULTURAL DATA” LECTURE AT THE EUROPEAN SUMMER UNIVERSITY IN DIGITAL HUMANITIES SESSION REPORT

Written by Ana Inkret, CESSDA/UL-ADP

Background

This report concerns a [lecture by Franciska de Jong](#) at the 2019 [European Summer University in Digital Humanities](#) at the University at Leipzig. The session took place on 2 August 2019 at the lecture hall of the Bibliotheca Albertina at the University of Leipzig, Germany.

This lecture is part of the series of stakeholder events, showcasing SSHOC project activities and achievements. It targeted young researchers in arts and humanities and computer sciences in particular.

Event Overview & Format

The lecture was one of the five public lectures by renowned specialists in Digital Humanities at the 2019 ["Culture & Technology" European Summer University in Digital Humanities](#) at the University of Leipzig.

The summer school is organised by a team at Leipzig University, led by Prof. Dr. Elizabeth Burr. It has been taking place since 2009 and is an established summer programme that brings together young scholars from the humanities, engineering and information sciences, providing a space for the discussion and acquisition of new knowledge, skills and competences in the broader context of Digital Humanities. Summer school also responds to the little recognized potential for development and innovation that would arise from a closer interaction between computer sciences and humanities. It further addresses the so-called gender divide between the “hard” and “soft” disciplines. [1]

In 2019, the programme consisted of workshops, lectures, a panel discussion, project presentations, poster session, and cultural programme. Several elements, including the lectures, were open to outside audiences without a participation fee. In addition, the lectures were live-streamed and the videos were later published on Zenodo.

The invited talks provide a theoretical and historical framework for the workshops that are the main part of the summer school. The lecturers “have done pioneer work in the Digital Humanities, have advanced the field in a special way or are giving considerable distinction to it.” [2] The talks in 2019 addressed the development of different aspects of digital humanities in Russia (by Irina Kizhner, Siberian Federal University), Brazil (Ricardo M. Pimenta, Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology) and Cameroon (Evelyn Fogwe Chibaka, University of Buea), digital reason (Michael

Sperberg-McQueen, Black Mesa Technologies LLC, USA), and methodology of Computational Literary Studies. Franciska de Jong's lecture was the closing lecture of the summer school.

The summer school had about 90 international participants from all over the world. The target audience are students in their final year, graduates, postgraduates, doctoral students, postdocs, teachers, librarians, and technical assistants who are involved in the theoretical, experimental or practical application of computational methods in the various areas of the Humanities, in libraries and archives, as well as engineers and computer scientists interested in computational methods in the Humanities. Though no information on the attendance of the lecture is available, it can be assumed that it was not limited to the participants of the summer school.

Lecture: Key Points

Language as social and cultural data

Speaker: Franciska de Jong (CLARIN)

Main points. The recent surge of data that is available through online platforms has given rise to new research agendas that have an increased potential for comparative research of cultural and societal phenomena across the boundaries of languages and modalities. These agendas come with a demand for the renewal of methodological frameworks and new models of multidisciplinary collaboration.

Based on a number of case studies (NLP for social surveys, question banks, parliamentary data), partly derived from the H2020 cluster project SSHOC (Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud), it was explained how research infrastructures can contribute to the emerging paradigms for studying social and cultural dynamics based on language data. The demands for integrating heterogeneous data types in particular were highlighted, such as a combination of spoken and textual resources, language data and numerical data, and multimodal signals.

Link to video recording: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3402109>

Outcomes & Feedback

The lecture was part of a prominent and well attended summer school, one of the few in the field of digital humanities that are organised in Europe. The contributions of the SSHOC project were presented in the context of EOSC to young professionals from all over the world. The opportunities to collaborate with the project partners in the multidisciplinary pilot work were highlighted, as was the Marketplace. Participants remarked upon the welcome and successful collaboration between the social sciences and humanities in the project during the discussion after the lecture. In general, the lectures were described by participants as “awesome”, “one of the highlights of the summer university”, “a serialized professional insight into the field”, and “stimulating” [3]. The presentation of the developing SSHOC project services, tools, and research potential of the cluster initiative to the young academics will certainly result in new users and new insights.

Resources

- [1] About ESU - Culture & Technology: Mission, accessible at <https://esu.fdhf.info/about-esu/#mission> (accessed 16 August 2021)
- [2] 2019: Lecturers, accessible at <https://esu.culintec.de/?q=node/1169> (accessed 16 August 2021)
- [3] Full reports of the ESU 2019 funded participants by DARIAH, accessible at <https://www.dariah.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Full-reports-of-the-ESU-2019-funded-participants-by-DARIAH.pdf> (accessed 16 August 2021)

ANNEX 3

EOSC SERVICES, COLLABORATIONS AND RDA EVENT REPORT

Written by Ana Inkret, CESSDA/UL-ADP

Background

This report concerns the discussion forum “[EOSC Services, Collaborations and RDA](#)” that took place on 21 October 2019 at the Aalto University at Espoo, Finland as one of the co-located events at the [Research Data Alliance 14th Plenary](#) in Helsinki, Finland. This event is part of the stakeholder series.

Workshop Overview & Format

The aim of the event was to bring together the communities of the EOSC cluster projects and the Research Data Alliance to discuss the commonalities and potential collaborations on community research data management solutions, aiming to identify and share best practices among the projects and communities.

The event was organised by WP2 and T6.2. It was chaired by Ron Dekker (CESSDA) and moderated by Vasso Kalaitzi (LIBER) and Ivana Ilijasic Versic (CESSDA). The following RDA and cluster project representatives participated in the debate: Daan Broeder (CLARIN-ERIC), Marco Molinaro (Italian National Institute for Astrophysics INAF), Mingfang Wu (Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), Jonathan Clark (DOI Foundation), Ornela De Giacomo (CERIC), Ron Dekker (CESSDA), René van Horik (DANS), Peter Wittenburg (Max Planck Computing and Data Facility), Franciska de Jong (CLARIN), Ari Asmi (University Helsinki), and Mirjam van Daalen (Paul Scherrer Institute).

The event was 4 hours long (including a break) and consisted of three panel discussions that focused on data services, connection to community organisations, and governance.

About 40 participants took part in the event.

Which EOSC clusters, if any, are of interest for you?

 22

What are the disciplines that interest you the most?

 24

Presentations & Discussions: Key Points

The main points of the presentations and discussion were summarized in the [official proceedings](#).

Link to slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3581075>

Outcomes & Feedback

While technical solutions and rapport with the user communities are specific to the cluster project, the discussion pointed to potential joint approach in the governance of the projects. In this, RDA can contribute to fostering collaboration, understanding governance in existing e-infrastructures, and influencing national funders through its international network.

A public follow-up meeting was planned, and the cluster agreed to hold regular quarterly meetings to identify opportunities for collaboration and share best practices.

A [blog post](#) was published along with the official report.

ANNEX 4

"Social & Cultural Data – taking the Users' Perspective" session at EOSC Symposium 2019 Session Report

Written by Ana Inkret, CESSDA/UL-ADP

Background

This report concerns the "Social & Cultural Data – taking the Users' Perspective" session at [EOSC Symposium 2019](#), titled "Where the EOSC makers & shakers meet". The session took place on 28 November 2019 in Budapest and was one of the events in the SSHOC stakeholder series.

Session Overview & Format

[EOSC Symposium 2019](#) took place from 26 to 28 November 2019 at Danubius Hotel Helia in Budapest, Hungary. The Symposium is one of the largest yearly EOSC events, part of EOSC Stakeholder Forum events. In 2019, it was co-organised by the EOSC secretariat project and the main ICT e-Infrastructures initiatives (EOSC-hub, GEANT, OpenAIRE and PRACE) in collaboration with the EOSC Governance Board, Executive Board and its Working Groups (Architecture, FAIR, Landscape, Rules of Participation, Sustainability.). The aim was to bring together all stakeholders to discuss the implementation of the EOSC and address questions such as "Is EOSC really contributing to the grand societal challenges addressed by science?" and "What is the role of national and thematic research infrastructures in the EOSC arena?".

The "[Social & Cultural Data – taking the Users' Perspective](#)" session was organised within the SSHOC project. The focus of the two-hour session was to discuss the perspectives of users working in the social and cultural data context to understand what their requirements are and how EOSC can support them.

The session was chaired by Ron Dekker (CESSDA) and featured presentations by Ilona von Stein (DANS-KNAW), Bela Janky (TÁRKI Foundation), Judit Gárdos (Centre for Social Sciences), Carsten Thiel (CESSDA), and Vasso Kalaitzi (LIBER). Session closed with a panel discussion on the topics of user needs, certification and trust, training, and sensitive data.

Even though [a list of all participants](#) of the Symposium is available, exact numbers for individual session were not recorded. The Mentimeter poll that was conducted during the session indicates that most participants came from university and library settings and that they were primarily acting as data managers.

Who are you? (Type of organization/work)

25

Are you a data user, data producer or data manager?

26

Presentations & Discussions: Key Points

The session was summarized in the official [proceedings](#).

Link to presentations: <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium2019/social-cultural-data-taking-users%E2%80%99perspective>

Outcomes & Feedback

The session was the only session of the symposium to focus on the perspective of humanities and social sciences and discuss the needs of users who work with social and cultural data. The extensive survey that was conducted as part of the panel discussion offered a valuable insight into the user habits and needs and provided helpful pointers for the upcoming SSHOC training programme.

Mentimeter Survey

Who are you? (Type of organization/work)

25

Are you a data user, data producer or data manager?

26

What repositories do you use to store and disseminate data?

Zenodo	DANS ❤️ 😊	gitlab http
Zenodo osf.io	Zenodo	I refer researchers to Re3data.
CESSDA national service providers	DSpace	Institutional, disciplinary

32

What repositories do you use to store and disseminate data?

Tárki, KDK	gitlab http	CESSDA consortium
national	zenodo local infrastructure	Institution repositories, gdrive, zenodo, dropbox
REAL - Repository of the Academy's Library	Local university repository	Institutional, disciplinary, Zenodo
Depends on which data !	B2SHARE	Open Science Framework (osf.io)
Figshare	Dataverse	B2share b2find
Institutional only so far.	Dspace	DSpace
Dataverse	FSD national data repository	B2find
Osf	For research data underlying a publication I will use a certified trustworthy data repository	

As a data user I check the provenance of the data by checking

17

As a data producer – when I share my data, I

18

To share my data, I store them

19

I will assign a PID to my data

20

Preparing Research Data

21

When looking for (new) data

21

How much do I invest for a dataset for which I only have the owner's description?

If it's not online, I'll ignore it.

There and back within a working day.

Quite far if it seems promising.

17

What authentication mechanisms are acceptable?

18

Which is the more helpful approach?

 18

Do you work with sensitive data?

 19

In your opinion, how could access to sensitive data be regulated?

Are you interested in training around EOSC and/or SSHOC?

17

What kind of training initiatives and training materials do you know of that are useful for your work and domain?

coursera	Best practices, case studies, protocols	Foster, OpenAIRE, google
OpenScienceMOOC MediArXiv	CESSDA, FOSTER, DCC, ANDS	Foster Open Science
CE	Data sensitivity	projects
Anonimizing data		

 10

What are the topics (regarding training) that need attention when we talk about social and cultural data science?

RDM	standards, sustainability of data	-
focus on ethics with regards to sensitive data		

 4

What type of training would you expect from the SSHOC project?

14

In your opinion, what kind of training tools and formats are effective?

5

What kind of activities would you like SSHOC to organize to reinforce the SSH Training network?

11

How do you find training or training materials?

Generic online research (e.g. Google)

Ask a colleague/my network

Research papers

Specific online research (e.g. DARIAH website, LIBER website, EOSC Portal, relevant project websites, etc.)

Other

11

How could this discovery process be improved?

metadata

services

 2

Should there be certification for SSHOC/EOSC training?

 10

Could you suggest an organisation to act as SSH training node in your region?

irina kuchma
opensciencemooc
sofia university
stabi hamburg

 4

In what way could EOSC support users working in the social and cultural data context?

None

expand the scope to go beyond data focus to include more of the Humanities

 2

Summary of the session (excerpt from the proceedings)

Social & Cultural Data – Taking the Users' Perspective

Chair: Ron Dekker, CESSDA & EOSC EB

Iona von Stein, DANS opened this stimulating session by talking about FAIR data in trustworthy repositories. The research data ecosystem is not only made by digital objects: the context should be considered as well, so not just the content but also the repository, which preserves, manages and provides access to digital material. Trust is a central element and FAIR repositories enhance accessibility, she concluded.

Béla Janky, Tárki Foundation, Hungary, argued that researchers receive no incentive to produce and share user-friendly data. The question is if one should trust the results published in the journals. Popular press has reported on significant shortcomings, he said. The rise of open data / data sharing has supported this criticism and put constraints on data manipulation. However, users need comprehensive data collections on a specific issue.

Judit Gárdos, Centre for Social Sciences at the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, highlighted

the importance of requesting consent when dealing with sensitive data. If this is missing, the issue can be solved through data anonymization. Although this is a useful practice, it is also expensive and leads to a loss of information, granularity and findability.

Understanding rules and policies is a fundamental condition for access. Carsten Thiel, CESSDA argued, travel is often needed to access data, especially in the case of libraries. The final goal should be to move data closer to users and to make it as user-friendly as possible. LIBER's Vasso Kalaitzi mentioned the SSHOC project, which is currently building an expertise strategy. SSHOC is broadening its network to external actors and stakeholders. It will contribute to the overall ecosystem of Training and Skills in the EOSC. The project is gathering existing training material in related projects in order to create the Train-the-Trainer Toolkit.

[Click here for the presentations from this session.](#)

Plenary 5 – Users at the center of EOSC

Chair: Anca Hienola, Finnish Meteorological Institute

The day continued with the Users at the centre of EOSC plenary session, where the panellists, Niklas Blomberg (EOSC-Life), Ron Dekker (SSHOC), Andreas Petzold (ENVRI-FAIR), Andy Gotz (PaNOSC), Giovanni Lamanna (ESCAPE), Emanuele Storti (Eurodoc) and Sverker Holmgren (The Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities) pointed out that EOSC is not one thing, nor an infrastructure, and it should have incentives for FAIR. Amidst the challenges in making EOSC more accessible, one widely recognised positive aspect of it is that thanks to it many researchers and infrastructures

think bigger, and outside of their community, as stated by Andreas Petzold.

Regarding users, according to Niklas Blomberg, the main question to ask shouldn't be "Who are the users?", but rather "What are the use cases?", since EOSC is not a one stop shop, and sometimes the same individual might work at different organisations or even has different positions. The panel agreed that researchers are getting increasingly familiar with EOSC, but they should be more engaged, and the users will go where they can trust the handling of data.

[Click here for the presentations from this session.](#)

ANNEX 5

REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD

Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond Conference Report

List of Authors

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Background

This report concerns the [Realising the European Open Science Cloud conference](#). The conference was the principal mid-project stakeholder event of the SSHOC project, planned to showcase SSHOC project results and engage with a wide range of stakeholders and initiatives. The 4-day virtual conference with 29 sessions was co-organised with EOSC-Hub and FREYA projects to maximise the reach and the interaction of the communities and to underline the collaboration and multidisciplinary of research developments, fostered by the projects.

The conference took place online from 16th to 19th November 2020.

Event Overview & Format

The [virtual conference](#) covered the topics of data policy and governance, technology and infrastructure, training and community building, and sustainability management with the objective to showcase the results achieved to date in each of the projects, to train the attendants to use the new tools and techniques developed to improve their data FAIRness and prepare the data and services to be aggregated into the EOSC Portal, and to identify and onboard new members to the project communities as well as to foster citizen science and collaborations with the industry.

The ambitious scope reflected the project aims of the organising projects. While the conference presented the main mid-term event for SSHOC, it was the concluding event for [FREYA](#) and [EOSC-Hub](#) projects. The main project representatives in the organisation board were Rob Carrillo (EOSC-Hub/Trust-IT), Ricarda Braukmann (FREYA/DANS), Marieke Willems (SSHOC/Trust-IT) and Irena Vipavc Brvar (SSHOC/CESSDA/UL-ADP), with many partners and associates from all three project contributing to the planning and execution of the event. The virtual conference platform was provided by vFairs company.

The four-day conference included panel discussions, breakout sessions, and networking opportunities in a virtual lounge. Each day focused on one of the main topics, with the final session of each day dedicated to the presentation of tools and services. Important addition to the conference programme was the EOSC Project EXPO, a virtual exhibition showcasing initiatives and projects of the European Open Science Cloud. Virtual exhibition booths of 30 exhibitors (including SSHOC) were open to visitors during the conference and offered, among other, downloadable materials and interactive features, including chat. A list of exhibitors is accessible at the [event website](#).

The [full agenda](#) is available on the event website, and an overview of the SSHOC-related sessions is added to this report. SSHOC project was part of 19 sessions (out of 29 in total). An additional session (SSHOC use-cases & communities) had to be cancelled due to unavailability of the speakers.

A total of 707 people participated in the event: 9 general administrators (members of the organising team), 129 booth administrators, and 570 attendees. 548 attendees provided information on their country of origin and the stakeholder category they identified with, allowing for the following conclusions: the event reached people in 49 countries, including 18 outside of Europe (with 30 participants in total, majority joining from Canada). Most represented European countries were the Netherlands (72 participants), Germany (61 participants), United Kingdom and Italy (each with 51 participants), France (41 participants), and Spain (with 39 participants).

Participation in Europe

Participants by country of origin

Participants in the Research and e-Infrastructures stakeholder category strongly prevailed (257 participants, 47%). Universities and research institutes (112 participants or 20%) as well as research libraries and archives (74 participants, 13,5%) were well represented. Participants belonging to the private sector and industry category were relatively numerous (39 participants or 7%), while researchers were fewer than might have been expected (48 participants or 9%). Citizen scientists (8 participants), policy makers (6 participants), and research funders (4 participants) were notably absent. Participation was highest in the joint panel sessions (with 190 participants at the most visited session) and lowest during the presentation of the tools, reflecting the distribution of the participants' categories and the fact that most of the tools and services have already been presented to their target audiences elsewhere. Data on participation in individual sessions was not recorded.

Participants by stakeholder groups

Presentations & Discussions at sessions with SSHOC involvement: Key Points

POLICY AND GOVERNANCE

Opening and keynote

Chair: Ricarda Braukmann (DANS)

Speakers: Ron Dekker (EOSC Executive Board, SSHOC), Liina-Maria Munari (EOSC Secretariat), Ingrid Dillo (DANS)

Main takeaway. EOSC projects work towards enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem. Many enabling services are created, not only in the context of EOSC projects but also in national and international contexts such as the RDA. The long-term availability of these solutions is at risk.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4275488 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4275498
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V8cfpmBoQjU

Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud

Chair: Owen Appleton (EGI), Bartosz Wilk (Cyfronet) and Marieke Willems (Trust-IT)

Speakers: Owen Appleton (EOSC-hub/EGI), Andreas Petzold (ENVRI-FAIR), Kay Graf (ESCAPE), Carole Goble (EOSC-Life), Tobias Richter (PANOSC) and Frank Fischer (SSHOC)

Main takeaway. Based on Owen Appleton's wrap-up of the session, some common topics and areas for future work were clearly identified.

Common topics

- Clear common interfaces and community standards are fundamental
- Automate what we can – reduce the human work to the remainder
- Build on what is already used and bring it to EOSC, not force a new manner of working
- Generic technical solutions from EOSC Core which can be tailored to thematic or regional community needs
- Thematic communities are providers and users of EOSC – dual role
- Sustainability and interoperation of EOSC Core to support further work by the thematic communities

Areas for future work

- Ensure low barriers to entry, convenience for users and providers
- Going out to the researchers, through clusters and finding other methods to engage them
- Incentives for participating: added value for users, sustainable operations for providers. Use case driven.
- Clarify incentives for opening data, reciprocity
- Common terminology for key entities: marketplace (is it commercial), onboarding, integration, composability
- Collaboration versus competition, what ensures sustainability
- Identify where interoperability / interconnection makes sense and brings benefit (not for its own sake)
- Deal with community legacies – bring them forward without breaking their workflows
- Clarity in levels of openness - embargoes, sensitive data, IPR issues etc. – as well as linked rules of participation
- Integrate knowledge and training with services and data
- Harmonise the Harmonisation already existing within thematic communities

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4277601
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jpWU9qVnY5o

FAIR Data-Citation for Social Sciences and Humanities

Chair: Nicolas Larrousse (Huma-Num)

Speakers: Barbara McGillivray (Alan Turing Institute), Jan Brase (Georg-August-Universität Göttingen), Angelo Riva (EURHISFIRM), Ami Saji (Sciences Po)

Main takeaways. Data Citation has moved from obscurity to the spotlight and at the very core of research. FAIR Data Citation should be the default mode of publication to ensure reproducibility and reusability of the data. One of the main challenges for FAIR Data Citation within the SSH is the diversity of the disciplines and the lack of incentives for researchers.

Links to materials

Video recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SiWLEWBjKCs&t=120s>

SSHOC Innovations in Data Production

Chair: Diana Zavala (UPF)

Speakers: Diana Zavala (UPF), Roxane Roussel (CNRS), Yuri Pettinicchi (MPG), Isabelle Cao (CNRS), Livio de Luca (CNRS)

Main takeaways:

MCSQ:

- Building resources such as the MCSQ (Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires) is an important first step for developing other resources for downstream computational linguistic applications, such as domain-specific machine translation models, predictors of question complexity, etc.
- The MCSQ is an important resource for doing quantitative linguistics analysis in survey text. Researchers working in such topics don't have to look for text in the PDFs, copy and paste, pre-process and align the text themselves because this has all been done in MCSQ and it is available to everyone, free of charge.
- Domain-specific code has been developed for relevant tasks such as sentence alignment and this is also available to the public (in my GitHub).
- Providing open-access data in an easy to access format stimulates studies in the area.
- MCSQ and its interface were completely developed using open source tools, no proprietary tools used in any of the steps.

ATV tool:

- Machine translation verification as an extra tool to improve survey quality.
- Expected efficiency gains.
- Improving training data to reduce false-positive rates.

Aioli tool:

The Aioli tool for annotation of cultural heritage objects is

- based on the democratization of photogrammetry techniques, which allow users to compute a 3D model by correlation of images, and the possibility of massively processing and sharing gathered data through the cloud.

- enables a multi-temporal analysis, to allow a follow-up on the state of its conservation and possible degradation. From simple photographs, the application generates a 3D representation of the object, which can directly be enriched with semantic annotations or additional resources related to the object.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279862
	Video recording: https://youtu.be/C4-WzL0dXwQ

Implementing FAIR data principles - The Ethnic and Migrant Minorities' Survey registry

Chair: Laura Morales and Ami Saji (Sciences Po)

Speakers: Laura Morales and Ami Saji (Sciences Po)

Main takeaways. The EMM (Ethnic and Migrant Minorities') Survey Registry is a free online tool that allows a wide-range of users to learn about and discover existing quantitative surveys undertaken with EMM (sub) populations. This tool has been designed by the ethnic and migration studies community to help make EMM survey data FAIR and, in turn, uncap their full potential for research and policymaking.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4274906
	Video recording: https://youtu.be/OY3FQWEcd60

TECHNOLOGY AND INFRASTRUCTURE

How can I onboard my resource to EOSC?

Chair: Owen Appleton (EGI)

Speakers: Owen Appleton (EGI/EOSC-hub), Carsten Thiel (CESSDA/SSHOC), Bartosz Wilk (CYFRONET), George Papastefanatos (University of Athens)

Main takeaways. Rather than onboarding of services, the session discussed the process of connecting resources (data, services, training, and software) to the EOSC ecosystem and community. Speakers presented the experience of curating a set of sustainable services for SSH researchers within the SSHOC project; the high level onboarding process and the new provider and resource profiles; the new provider portal which will be used for onboarding; and the upgraded EOSC Marketplace.

Links to materials	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=32hgvCEhsrM
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EOSC Interoperability: Architecture and FAIR Data Aspects

Chair: Johannes Reetz (MPCDF)

Speakers: Hervé l'Hours (ESSEX), Giacinto Devito (INFN), Mari Kleemola (TUNI)

Main takeaways. In order to ensure FAIR and interoperable data in the future and in the long run, we must act now. A lot of technical and content wise work has been already done on the topic: implementing FAIR principles when preparing a dataset, becoming a trustworthy repository, approved by the CoreTrustSeal commission, and various EOSC services, but communities, services and resources can be more connected as they are at this point. Panellists made some examples of their work on how to improve interoperability and fairness of research data in the future. This session was an introduction to the following breakout sessions.

Links to materials	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s19eQkv1Pns
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FAIR Data Implementation: Extending the portfolio of EOSC services with FAIR data repositories

Chair: Johannes Reetz (MPCDF)

Speakers: Hervé l'Hours (University of Essex), Olivier Rouchon (CINES)

Main takeaways. Long-term preservation repositories focus on the challenges bound to archiving digital objects over time. With the rise of the FAIR principles, new services have flourished around the research data, but what is FAIR today may not be FAIR in the long run, so the question on “how to tackle this issue” stays quite relevant. To enable trust from users and data depositors, certification will be the ultimate step to lock this (e.g. CoreTrustSeal which supports researchers when thinking about their data in the future). Achieving CoreTrustSeal demonstrates Trustworthy Data Repository status and emerging EOSC work is aligning repository maturity with the ability to enable FAIRness. SSHOC project is one project undertaking repository support with a view to increasing certification, sharing best practice and moving towards an active community of EOSC trusted repositories.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279252 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312840
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7PpXPVQWJzA

Metadata Interoperability: SSHOC and Beyond

Chair: Mari Kleemola (Tampere University)

Speakers: Mari Kleemola (Tampere University), Claudia Martens (DKRZ)

Main takeaway: Session was built around “standards meeting reality”, covering solutions to current challenges and improvements proposed while noting heterogeneity in data and solutions across service providers and archives.

Links to materials	Slides: http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279855 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4277667
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KPZjr2_CMDw

Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC

Chairs: Laure Barbot (DARIAH) and Yoann Moranville (DARIAH)

Speakers: Laurent Capelli (TRIPLE/CNRS, Huma-Num), Virginie Ngo (TRIPLE/CNRS, Huma-Num), Matej Ďurčo, (SSHOC/ACDH-CH), Dieter Van Uytvanck (SSHOC/CLARIN), Frank Fischer (SSHOC/DARIAH), Arnaud Gingold (TRIPLE/OpenEdition), Tomasz Parkoła (SSHOC/PSNC), Aleksandra Nowak (SSHOC/PSNC), Suzanne Dumouchel (TRIPLE/CNRS, Huma-Num)

Main takeaways: SSH Open Marketplace and the TRIPLE discovery platform are complementary and not competitive (tools and services on one side + training and datasets/projects / profiles on the other side).

This session is part of a common work that started at the previous TRIPLE consortium meeting (October 2020) to enhance collaboration between both projects/platforms. Next step is a longer workshop between both teams to discuss issues.

Creation of a short task force was proposed to identify common topics. The SSHOC and TRIPLE projects had already agreed to study synergy of the two ingestion pipelines and to work together on vocabularies which is a challenging topic. There is no interest to duplicate the work. A common work should also be done toward the quality of metadata and how to incite aggregators to improve the quality of their metadata.

It is important to share the knowledge and to keep the TRIPLE and SSHOC project teams updated of the development versions and need to align each other's work.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4277601
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hr94Yz8odPE

Thematic Services for Social Sciences and Humanities & SSHOC WP3 Lifting Technologies into the SSH Cloud

Chairs: Debora Testi (CINECA) and Daan Broeder (KNAW)

Speakers: Emanuel Dima (Eberhard Karls University Tuebingen), Willem Elbers (CLARIN ERIC), Pavel Stranak (LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ), Davor Davidović (Ruđer Boskovic Institute), Daan Broeder (KNAW)

Main takeaways. From a researcher’s perspective, the maturity of the presented services is high not only for natural language processing but also for broader Social Sciences and Digital Humanities research. Researchers are able to use CLARIN/SSHOC web services such as UDPipe, which is a language processing tool with one of the broadest linguistic scopes on the market, without any prior background knowledge in programming. Furthermore, such services are highly interoperable; UDPipe is part of CLARIN’s Language Resource Switchboard and as such can be used to process texts in conjunction with several other Switchboard services that are crucial for research that goes beyond linguistics, such as stylometric tools for discourse analysis. In the future, the CLARIN Switchboard aims to become integrated with other repositories and services such as the SSHOC Switchboard, which will further facilitate the inclusion of new language technologies and resources with an even broader interdisciplinary scope.

Links to materials	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gswy3gDDLpl
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Dataverse, Adaptation to the European Research Environment

Chair: Marion Wittenberg (DANS)

Speaker: Laura Huis in 't Veld (DANS)

Main takeaways. Dataverse is Open Source Software, and a repository software for sharing and publishing datasets.

Developing a translation service for translation of the user interface in the European languages. Weblate, also an Open Source Software, is adapted to the needs of the SSHOC project.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279182
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jyNZ5gDcaDg

TRAINING AND COMMUNITY BUILDING

Community Building Examples Across EOSC-hub, FREYA, & SSHOC

Chair: Timea Biro (RDA Europe)

Speakers: Timea Biro (RDA Europe), Frances Madden (FREYA), Ellen Leenarts (SSHOC), Iryna Kuchma (OpenAIRE), Rene van Horik (EOSC-Hub), Gergely Sipos (EOSC-Hub)

Main takeaway: There is a need for more coordination between the various communities to ensure collaboration and integration of approaches, rather than a dispersed approach and repetition.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279221 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4282622 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4280604 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4282149
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BEr6kG-bnk

Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?

Chair: Helene Schwalm (University of Bordeaux)

Speakers: Thomas Kaarsted (SDU), Dirk van Gorp (RU Library), Ad Pollé (Europeana), Tim Causer (UCL)

Main takeaways: The session provided an overview of what Citizen Science is, how research libraries have an essential role to play in its deployment through the BESPOC model and other means, acting as knowledge broker and facilitator among others. At the same time, several citizen science and crowdsourcing projects/activities were presented. At the panel session, possible collaborations were uncovered and a follow-up discussion could include the relation and interaction between EOSC and Citizen Science.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4290145 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4290605 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4290247
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iqHwZNOaLsU

Engaging the Private Sector: Roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC services

Chair: Sy Holsinger (EGI), Elisa Cauhé (EGI), Marieke Willems (Trust-IT)

Speakers: Sy Holsinger (EGI), Marcin Plociennik (PSNC), Daniel Alonso Roman (ITI, EUH4D), Martin Kaltenböck (SWC)

Main takeaway: The session discussed engagement strategies to increase uptake of EOSC services in the Private Sector. EOSC-hub presented the success stories and use cases of the EOSC Digital Innovation Hub, discussing roadblocks and best practices in fostering collaboration with and uptake by the private sector of EOSC services with EOSC-hub and SSHOC with the audience. SSHOC brings the experience from private sector partner and service provider Semantic Web Company to the discussion. Final recommendations for the EOSC in engaging the private sector, based on the lessons learned from the EOSC-DIH and discussion with services providers and users, are:

- EOSC and private sector stakeholders have to speak with each other.
- Try to find synergies with existing initiatives.
- Do not reinvent, but work together and be complimentary, and strengthen the initiative.

Links to materials	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3MEgawbhPXL
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SSHOC and Archaeology: Learning from the ARIADNE Portal

Chairs and speakers: Holly Wright (ADS), Julian Richards (University of York)

Main takeaway: ARIADNE portal and services cater to a heterogeneous research discipline with a large range of data types. The ARIADNEplus project has been answering the needs of the community, offering solutions for an improved data availability, and mapping data descriptions. Project also focuses on embedding into EOSC.

Links to materials	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=THOgEgbeHto
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SSHOC Surveycodings

Chair: Kea Tijdens (UvA)

Speakers: Maurice Martens (CENTERDATA), Verena Ortmanns (GESIS), Giovanni Borghesan (UVT)

Main takeaway. Surveycodings provides large sets with classified responses in several languages. Respondents can more easily detect their initial response can't be classified and hence rephrase. The set is generated by experts and versioned for future reference.

Links to materials	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vIGGGQB4898&t=661s
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SUSTAINABILITY AND FUTURE

Challenges in Sustainability of FAIR Research Data and Services for SSH and Beyond

Chairs: Sergio Andreozzi (EOSC-hub) and Irena Vipavc (SSHOC)

Speakers: Simon Lambert (FREYA), Franciska de Jong (SSHOC), Tiziana Ferrari (EOSC-hub), Suzanne Dumouchel (SSHOC Marketplace), Lydia Borrell-Damian (EOSC Sustainability WG)

Main takeaways:

- Projects have to be able to identify the costs of the services in order for them to be maintained beyond the project's life. It is important that part of the clusters are those organisation that are stable beyond the project - e.g. ERICs because they have experience and responsibility to do this.
- A lot of national data providers with a keen interest in supporting open science experience a clash between open science policy and the availability of funding to implement it. In order to make thematic services sustainable we need a shift in how national funding is erogated. It is important that the funding scheme for communities and clusters continues. The real scientific progress and breakthrough come from the grassroots initiatives that is why they need to be well funded and supported.
- EOSC needs now to put the researcher at the centre - if they find EOSC useful its success will be assured.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4306648 Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yxPk_c6AJL8&t=160s
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EOSC in Practice: From a Research Communities' Perspective

Chair: Marieke Willems (Trust-IT)

Speakers: Slava Tykhonov (DANS), Ami Saji (ETHMIGSURVEYDATA, SciencesPo), Cees van der Eijck (UNOTT), Emiliano Degl'Innocenti (CNRS), Alberto Melloni (UNESCO chair in the field of Religious Studies, RESILIENCE coordinator)

Main takeaways: Thematic and (inter)disciplinary research communities will join in this discussion on addressing the opportunities and challenges that they encounter when contributing to EOSC by implementing principles, procedures, tools and services developed.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4281101 Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qIZxWmgzaaM
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Closing Remarks

Chair: Rob Carrillo (Trust-IT)

Speakers: Tiziana Ferrari (EOSCHub), Simon Lambert (Freya), Ron Dekker (CESSDA)

Main takeaways: Realising EOSC was a truly international event, recreating some of the exchanges and interactions of a live meeting. It provided a very successful platform for dissemination of results (marking for example over 3780 booth visits and 1520 document views at the project exposition). Organisers awarded the most active participants and the best booths (ENVRI-FAIR, FAIR for Health Research, and EOSC DIH as the runners-up and NEANIAS project as the best booth). The three projects' representatives closed the conference.

Links to materials	Video recording: https://youtu.be/qlZxWmgzaaM?t=5151
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Outcomes & Feedback

Realising European Open Science Cloud brought the EOSC community together in the comprehensive and interactive presentations and discussions of the current state of the EOSC ecosystem. The successful collaboration of the three projects enhanced the respective project achievements by placing them in a wider context of the European FAIR research data landscape. The interactive interface of the event, the networking and the gamification features also fostered an important sense of belonging to a community for the participants, speakers and presenters, which was especially valuable in the time of restricted travel and personal contact.

The strong community-building and -representation were noted by the participants. Though the post-event survey (see below) only had 13 responses, participants noted the importance of the overview that was offered, describing the event as “very informative and inspiring” and confirming that they got “a good overview on the activities” and a “better understanding of who's doing what in the EOSC world”. This information is complemented by the activity on [Twitter](#).

The organisation of the event required close cooperation, several meetings, a shared working space, and a separate communication line during the event. The organisational challenges and lessons were later presented at the [SSHOC Training Community call](#).

The conference exposed the problem of reaching specific research communities and policy makers who are not necessarily the target audience of the overarching topics but rather of some of the individual sessions. Targeted promotion of chosen segments rather than the conference as a whole is recommended in the future.

All three projects reflected on the event from their specific points of view: [FREYA](#) from the PID perspective, [EOSC-Hub](#) provided a detailed overview, and [SSHOC](#) focused on the project-related sessions. Blogs detailing the involvement of [LIBER](#) and the [NEANIAS](#) project should also be mentioned.

The materials from the sessions and the exposition continue to be available for use on [YouTube](#) and [Zenodo](#).

Overview of SSHOC Sessions

Overview of plenary and SSHOC sessions

with links to session descriptions

16. 11. Policy and governance

9:30 [Opening and keynote](#)

11:00 [Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud](#)

13:30-14.30 [FAIR Data-Citation for Social Sciences and Humanities](#)

15:15 [SSHOC Innovations in Data Production: Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires, Automated Translation Verification Tool, Aioli platform](#)

16:00 [Implementing FAIR Data Principles: The Ethnic and Migrant Minorities' Survey Registry](#)

17.11. Technology and Infrastructure

9:30 [How can I onboard my resource to EOSC?](#)

11:30 [EOSC Interoperability: Architecture and FAIR Data Aspects](#)

12:00 [FAIR Data Implementation: Extending the portfolio of EOSC services with FAIR data repositories](#)

12:00 [Metadata Interoperability: SSHOC and beyond](#)

14:00 [Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC](#)

14:00 [Thematic services for social sciences and humanities & SSHOC WP3 lifting technologies into the SSH Cloud](#)

16:00 [Dataverse, adaptation to the European research environment](#)

18.11. Training and Community building

9:30 [Community Building Examples Across EOSC-hub, FREYA, & SSHOC](#)

11:30 [Citizen Science: what it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?](#)

11:30 [Engaging the Private Sector. About roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC services](#)

16:00 [SSHOC and Archaeology: Learning from the ARIADNE Portal](#)

16:00 [SSHOC Surveycodings](#)

19.11. Sustainability and Future

9:30 [Challenges in Sustainability of FAIR Research Data and Services for SSH and Beyond](#)

11:30 [EOSC in practice. From a research communities' perspective](#)

13:00 [Closing remarks](#)

Post-event Survey

Out of all participants only 13 responded to the post-event Survey. Overall rate of the event was high (average 4.5 on a scale 1-5). Organizational aspects (in terms of time management, length, venue) were rated even higher (average 4.8).

Participants learned about the event from:

- Social media
- Through SSHOC

- Newsletter
- FREYA Ambassador Competition
- Blue-Cloud project, as a booth holder
- Through ENVRI FAIR
- E-mail from colleagues
- From supervisor
- From cluster communication channel
- It was recommended after another webinar

<i>Do you see this event having a positive impact on your work and how?</i>
It brought many people from the EOSC community together and allowed some interaction in these difficult times.
yes, good to see the presentations
a good opportunity to get an overview. with the virtual conference participation also the effort to participate is minimised. Despite missing to meet the colleagues and having options for more in depth discussion this kind of overview is very important and inspiring.
A lot of interesting presentations and materials from the booths (documents, movies)
Better understanding of who's doing what in the EOSC world.
I learned more about some projects and the work they've done and their results. The FREYA project and the work they've done on PID will be especially useful in one of my projects.
Yes, I got many good tips on PIDs and a lot of good information around FREYA
It was very good to get information on the current situation with the EOSC projects
Yes, it was very informative and inspiring.

<i>What did you miss or could be improved from the event?</i>
The public chat function seemed a bit confusing at times.
sometimes very technical but a good overview on the activities
I couldn't sign in for some sessions. It was an information, that it will start soon and it was more than 30 min late
I know it's hard in a webinar format, but the collaboration chat room didn't really gain much momentum. I hoped to make new connections and maybe start brainstorming about HorizonEurope projects. Maybe next time.
A bit more interactive. It's still a really good first try for an all in virtual conference. I think there was also a bit of a lack of communication around this event. I didn't find out about it through my usual channels.

Nothing that I can think of right now.

I think the booths were very nice, but the chat was not very easily usable - even having "subjects" as trees, or more private chat would make users more likely to participate.

I couldn't find a direct link to the event in daily e-mail reminders.

ANNEX 6

SSHOC WORKSHOP: SSH CODE OF CONDUCT

Workshop Report

Written by Veronika Keck, CESSDA/GESIS

Background

This report concerns a workshop that was organized by NSD and supported by UL-ADP, LIBER, and GESIS. The event was titled “SSH Code of Conduct”. This virtual event was held on the 17th of March 2021.

The announcement and event information are available [here](#) and the presentations have been uploaded to the dedicated SSHOC Community on [Zenodo](#).

Organizers

From the SSHOC project task 6.2: Irena Vipavc, Ana Inkret (both CESSDA/UL-ADP), Iris Buunk (LIBER), and Veronika Keck (GESIS) were involved in the technical organisation and support during the event.

For the content of the workshop, the following speakers planned and delivered the presentations: Mathilde Steinsvaag Hansen (NSD), Ina Nepstad (NSD), Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI-ERIC). Siri Tenden, Marianne Høgetveit Myhren and Ingvild Eide Graff (all NSD) were also involved in leading the discussion.

Workshop Overview & Format

The virtual workshop streamed via ZOOM was designed as a 2,5-hours event. It started with an introduction of the speakers and a Mentimeter survey on participant’s expectations and opinions regarding the common GDPR and guidelines for research.

What are your expectations for today?

Mentimeter

10

Do you think it is a good idea to have common GDPR guidelines for research, to be compliant with GDPR?

Mentimeter

16

It was followed by three presentations (10-30 min long), a lively Q&A part, break-out sessions for expert discussions, and a plenary session at the end.

The three presentations during the workshop included the following:

- Presentation of findings from SSHOC report on the impact of the GDPR and its implications for EOSC
- Anatomy of a Code of Conduct and Implications for GDPR
- Creation of a Code of Conduct in health research

The workshop finished with some take-home messages and a wrap-up.

Participants

35 participants attended the workshop. Of them, fourteen universities and research performing institutions, seven identified as researchers, four came from libraries and archives, and three identified as research & e-infrastructure and EOSC thematic clusters (see graphic below).

Presentations & Discussions: Key Points

1. Presentation of findings from SSHOC report on the impact of the GDPR and its implications for EOSC

Speakers: Ina Nepstad and Mathilde Steinsvåg Hansen, NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data

This presentation focused on the [SSHOC Deliverable 5.7](#). This Deliverable is a report on the impact of the GDPR on research and its implications for EOSC. The report describes and compares the national implementation of the GDPR across Europe by examining some European countries' national laws and conducting interviews with researchers. It also describes what implications GDPR might have for EOSC.

A part of the presentation covered processing of special categories of personal data. To lawfully process the special categories of personal data one would need a lawful basis that can be found under Art. 9 of the GDPR. The speaker stressed that it is prohibited to process sensitive data unless you have legal ground. It is common to use explicit consent or in a case of research the public interest/research purposes.

Which bases are to be used to lawfully process personal data depends on the purpose of use. The GDPR Art. 6 no.1 (e) is in some countries used for research purposes, that is researchers can process personal data, since their work is considered as the work done in the public interest, without documented consent from a person whose data are being used. This shows the need for the lawful processing of personal data in the public interest.

Further, the speaker stressed that some countries have provided lists of safeguards in addition to GDPR art. 89 (1), others have not. These varied approaches require standardization or a unified approach.

The speaker pointed out the following implications for EOSC:

- As all processing of personal data must have a legal ground, the different interpretations and supplements in national legislations might affect the users of EOSC.
- The wording in the consent given from the data subject to the researcher might cause hindering for sharing data with others, including through EOSC.
- A plan should be made for the assessment of personal data within EOSC.
- The required safety measures differ from one country to another. When organizing EOSC, a plan should be made for the assessment of the suggested safety measures is sufficient.

2. Anatomy of a Code of Conduct and Implications for GDPR

Speakers: Ina Nepstad and Mathilde Steinsvåg Hansen, NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data

In the second presentation, the keynote speaker introduced the concept of the Code of Conduct, its definition, and its relevance. The Code of Conduct can be defined as a set of voluntary accountability tools/guidelines which set out specific data protection rules for categories of controllers and processors. A Code, therefore, assists members of the specific Code with data protection compliance and accountability. The code will be applicable in specific sectors or relating to particular processing operations. It identifies and resolves key data protection challenges that are important to the sector, with insurance from supervision authorities that the code is appropriate. A code is written by an organization/association representing a sector in a way that the sector understands and enables the sector to solve these challenges. The basis for a Code of Conduct is regulated in GDPR art. 40 and 41.

A code of conduct is relevant because it will help the sector to comply with GDPR. It can be a useful and effective accountability tool, providing a detailed description of the most appropriate, legal, and ethical set of behaviors for a sector. From a data protection viewpoint, code can therefore operate as a rulebook for controllers and processors who design and implement GDPR compliant data processing activities. Developing a code of conduct can help build public trust and confidence in the concrete sector's ability to comply with data protection laws. Moreover, it can help to reflect on the processing activities and ensure that rules of a specific field are followed to achieve best practice. The creation of a Code of Conduct might be potentially cost-effective.

Creation of a Code of Conduct in health research

Speaker: Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, BBMRI ERIC

The BBMRI ERIC's presentation focused on a Code of Conduct for health research.

The EU General Data Protection Regulation entered into force on 25 May 2018, with direct effect in the Member States. Given that legal texts are not always easily accessible, BBMRI-ERIC, together with other stakeholders, considers the code of conduct as described in Art 40, 41 of the GDPR as a key tool to develop a guide for researchers and administrative staff (especially data controllers and processors) to reduce unnecessary fear relating to compliance and to enhance data sharing to stimulate research.

The purpose of the Code of Conduct for Health Research initiative is:

1. To contribute to the proper application of the regulation, taking into account the specific features of processing personal data in the area of health;
2. To clarify and specify certain rules of the GDPR for controllers who process personal data for purposes of scientific research in the area of health;
3. To help demonstrate compliance by controllers and processors with the regulation; and
4. To help foster transparency and trust in the use of personal data in the area of health research.

After the development of the Code of Conduct, it needs to be submitted for approval to a monitoring body. The requirements before submission as defined by the European data protection board include an explanatory statement, clear definition of the scope, identification of the monitoring body, demonstration of stakeholder consultations, confirmation about the compliance with applicable national legislation.

There are several criteria for approval of the submitted Code of Conduct. It should meet a particular need of that sector, facilitate the application of the GDPR, specify the application of the GDPR, provide sufficient safeguards, and provide effective mechanisms for monitoring the compliance of the code.

The process of submission and approval includes several feedback loops of the developed draft Code of Conduct. After a draft Code of Conduct has been submitted to a competent supervisory authority (cSA, typically national Data Protection Authority) that confirms European scope (transnationality) via cooperation procedure, the cSA will seek a maximum of two co-reviewers to assist with assessing that draft Code and will assist in preparation for submission to the EDPB. Before final approval of the draft Code, cSA amends the draft communicates any changes needed and the feedback loop starts. Once the feedback loop is finished, EDPB or cSA will communicate the approval or the rejection of the Code to all SAs as per the consistency mechanisms procedure.

The speaker provided step-by-step explanations about how the working group of BBMRI ERIC created a Code of Conduct in health research. Their Code does not promote one legal basis over another, as the decision is context-dependent and might have a specification in national law (country derogation). The presenter stressed that the anonymization of data is context-dependent. The key topics of the BBMRI ERIC Code of Conduct are legal basis/consent, personal data/anonymization, controller/joint controller/processor. The structure of the Code of Conduct is based on the FAQ style, where the question is followed by a rule/recommendation, then explanation, and an example. The language used is non-legalistic.

4. Key points from the Q&A session

One of the topics of the Q&A session was on the legal basis 'legitimate interest' (6.1(f)). Some researchers see the 'legitimate interest' as not an appropriate basis for research activities. According to the opinion of keynote speakers it is not sufficient to use data falling under Art. 9 GDPR for research.

Another topic was about the controller/joint controller/processor conundrum. One of the participants was sceptical about whether this can be regulated in a Code of Conduct in a binding way. The arising question in this regard was whether it is more an issue of fact.

One of the speakers agreed with this statement but also suggested that roles can be attributed, so there is leeway in designing a project and the roles of partners. The suggestion was to provide Guidelines on the function and the consequences.

Another keynote speaker underlined that the purpose of the Code of Conduct is clarification, assistance to provide control information. It has been stated that in general there is a willingness to be a controller/joint controller.

One of the participants commented that the Code of Conduct cannot change the GDPR and fill gaps, provide legal bases, or redefine the concept of the controller. It can only “translate” it to researchers. It can only propose scenarios, examples for some directions for researchers.

Take away message: Code of Conduct is a tool for education and organic work in the community.

An interesting point was whether BBMRI considered the option that ERIC could be the monitoring body. Presenters agreed that this has been considered, however it is not the first option because ERIC cannot act independently. If Code is a tool for education, it should be trustworthy. One of the participants suggested outsourcing this obligation to be a monitoring body to organizations providing industrial code, law firms, or private sector bodies. One of the remarks was that the Code of Conduct can be agreed upon by countries but there is still specific regulation for each country regarding how the Code is applicable in a specific country.

Take away message: The scope of the code is to clarify GDPR, anonymization, etc. The general Code of Conduct is of European scope that should be communicated to national authorities. It should be reviewed on the European level and therefore it is subject to approval by European bodies.

5. Key messages from experts’ discussions in breakout rooms:

The discussion continued in three breakout rooms. This section summarizes the common answers from the participants. The experts were provided with a list of questions for discussion that are listed below.

1. Our understanding is that different legal basis for the processing of personal data is being used in research projects. Which legal basis do you think is the best fit for research and why?

In some countries, e.g. Finland and UK the most commonly used legal basis is a public interest, while in others, e.g. Norway, it is more common to use consent, whenever possible. Public interest is only used for practical reasons when informed consent is not possible. We do, however, see a movement lately towards the increased use of public interest in Norway as well.

2. Do you believe that the choice of a legal basis for processing personal data in research, is based on ethical considerations? For instance: is consent being used as a legal basis for the processing of personal data, because there might be demands of consent in ethical guidelines?

Ethical consent is widely misunderstood as the legal basis. Though public interest might be the legal basis, the fact that one is still required to gather ethical consent in many projects confuses many.

3. Our understanding is that national legislation across Europe presents different terms in relation to which appropriate safeguards are required when a public interest/scientific or historical research purposes are being used as a legal basis, cf. art. 89 nr. 1. Which terms should be necessary when processing research data and why?

National legislation across Europe differs on the required safeguards when a public interest/scientific or historical research purposes are being used as a legal basis, cf. art. 89 nr. 1. When processing research data, several safeguards that should be used are named in GDPR, e. g. encryption and de-identification of personal data.

4. Which challenges/limitations have you experienced in relation to the possible reuse and/or storage of research data, containing personal data?

The single most common problem in terms of reusing data is the lack of information being given to the data subjects at the start of the original research project. They are often not informed of the intention of re-using the data at a later stage, which makes such recycling impossible. To make sure that they receive information about the planned re-use of the data would go a long way in making more data available.

5. Which challenges/limitations have you experienced in relation to sharing research data containing personal data across borders (within EU/EEA)?
Both ethical considerations and privacy considerations dictate that information should be provided to participants in research projects. Can you think of/have you experienced any challenges when trying to harmonize GDPR information and ethical information?

Though GDPR aims at harmonizing information requirements and safety measures, national legislation may still vary between European countries. Specific demands in various countries may render sharing across borders difficult if they include strict safety measures which are uncommon in other countries.

Outcomes & Feedback

Take-home messages from the workshop about the SSH Code of Conduct:

1. Further support of harmonization and consistent implementation of the GDPR across the EU is warranted
2. The terms and conditions for processing sensitive personal data vary from one country to another, but the common denominator in most countries is the importance of ensuring that the processing of special categories of personal data is subject to adequate safeguards, cf. Article 89 (1)
3. A mutual understanding as to what measures will satisfy the requirement of appropriate measures (“suitable, specific, technical, organizational”) pursuant to Article 89 (1) would make sharing of research data across borders easier

4. Example of developing a Code of Conduct in the health research field shows that it is a long process requiring the participation of experts in consultation with the public: a. on an individual level (esp. use cases on a case-by-case basis), b. on sections of the code via reference groups, c. on the whole code and submission process
5. Useful link: [European Data Protection Board Register for Codes of Conduct](#).

Media coverage and promotion of SSHOC

[Announcements](#) were shared on the SSHOC website, mailing lists of the SSHOC Training Community, and individual organisations. The keynote speakers decided against live tweeting due to the closed character of the expert event. [Workshop notes](#) have been prepared afterward and distributed through the SSHOC networks.

Results from the evaluation

10 participants filled in the general SSHOC evaluation form (see next section).

Overall, the event was positively evaluated. Three participants evaluated the event as “excellent”, three said it was “very good” and four stated it was “good” when rating the overall event. The organization was evaluated as “very well organized” by six participants, “excellently organized” and “good organized” by two respondents each.

Similarly positive was the feedback and rating with regards to the question of whether the event met participants’ expectations. Five participants reported that the event exceeded their expectations, three said that it matched expectations and two agreed that the workshop greatly exceeded their expectations.

The most common positive feedback was given with regards to the presentations, their comprehensiveness, and awareness-raising character. Followed by the organization and format of the even, possibility to discuss in small groups, as well as a big variety of countries and experiences represented that is shown in the graphic below:

Responding to the question of what could have been better, participants indicated that while enjoying the more specific topic-related third presentation, with insights and examples coming from the experience of the speaker, the first two “introductory presentations were too generally structured on the matter discussed”. Participants wished for better time management in the breakout rooms, where they had “far too many questions for the discussion”.

What was further positive is that all respondents who have filled out the post-event survey have agreed that the event had a positive impact on their work. In particular, respondents reported that they found the workshop to be “inspiring”, e.g. for their work on the ethical dimension of a research project they are engaged in currently. They reported that “the webinar gave a broad overview of the ideas in this field” and “increased their network” and broadened their perspective on “a variety of different approaches to the code of conduct process by listening to the other participants”.

Suggestions for future workshops

In general, the setup of the 2,5-hours workshop with several break-out rooms and one coffee break needs further conceptual development because a lot of people stayed only for the main presentations that were given for about one hour, and about a half of the participants have left during the coffee break before even the breakout room discussions have started. One of the comments stated that “It's difficult for people to reserve 2-3 hours, now in busy schedules!”

A possible solution to this conceptual problem is to “save” an attractive plenary speech as the last point of the agenda to keep the participants during the complete event.

Results from the post-event evaluation survey

What did you hope to gain from the workshop/webinar?
A lot of knowledge concerning every day practice for GDPR and research ethics
Ideas, see how others are tackling the issues on GDPR; how could code of conduct help researchers in daily work
Contacts with stakeholders interested in a CoC
New information

The learn more about the work that is being done in different European countries
Better understanding of the data protection requirements in social research.
More answers about legal aspects of open science.
Insight in the process for development of a code
Increased knowledge about the code of conduct work and also about dilemmas around legal basis and ethical considerations
To gain a clearer idea of how to construct a policy in EU projects

Do you see this workshop/webinar having a positive impact on your work and how?
Yes, some issues have been clarified
See that it really takes time to implement and there is a huge need for training.
Yes.
Yes
by streamlining the work across the EU

For sure it was inspiring for my work on the ethical dimension of a research project I am engaged in currently.
Yes, practical experience of other participants can be implemented.
Yes, the webinar gave a broad overview of the ideas in this field.
Yes, it increased my network. By listening to the other participants, I also acknowledge a great variety of different approaches to the code of conduct process.
I certainly see this event as a way to get through shared good practices and principles on how to progress with anyone's specific tasks.

What did you like most about the workshop/webinar?
the small group
small rooms - possibilities to discuss
Michaela's presentation.
God format in general
The variety of countries and experiences represented
It was comprehensive and well prepared.
Involvement.
That BBMRI considers that the development of a code and awareness go hand in hand.
The presentations
I mostly liked the constant looking from the organizers for feedbacks from participants

What did you miss or could be improved at the workshop/webinar?
it was really good
Issue, that a lot of people stay only for the main presentation and leave when discussion has started. It's difficult for people to reserve 2-3 hours, now with busy schedules!!
Better time management -- far too many questions for the discussion session, and only enough time to discuss one or two in depth.

To encourage more people to share their experiences

I unfortunately missed the second part of the webinar due to the problems with the Internet connection, so it would be great to get some minutes/bullet points about the group discussions and results thereof.

/

I had to leave early, so I don't know what I missed.

It was a pity that the groups became very small and that only 4 ordinary participants were left in the last part of the workshop. We were 16 altogether during the last plenary session, but as far as I understood, 11 were from the organizers (including 7 from NSD)? This reduced the output. It might be a good idea to "save" an attractive plenary speech as the last point of the agenda to keep the participants during the complete event.

I think that some of the introductory presentations were too generally structured on the matter discussed, while I much enjoyed the more specific topic-related presentations, with insights and examples coming from the experience of the speaker.

ANNEX 7

THE ESFRI CLUSTERS AT RDA HOUSE OF COMMONS EVENT REPORT

Written by Ana Inkret, CESSDA/UL-ADP

Background

This report concerns [The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons](#) debate that took place online on 19 April 2021 as one of the co-located events at the [17th RDA Plenary](#). The event is part of the stakeholder series.

Workshop Overview & Format

The event was organised as a follow-up meeting for the SSHOC co-located event at the 14th RDA Plenary, [EOSC services, collaborations, and RDA](#). The aim was to discuss the past, present and future of the ESFRI Clusters collaboration during the journey of integrating thematic services into EOSC by debating data services, communities and end-users onboarding and governance. The organisers wanted to gather input from the members of the international RDA community, the ESFRI community, EOSC ecosystem, and data experts and domain researchers.

The event was organised by SSHOC WP2 and 6. It was opened by Ron Dekker (CESSDA) and moderated by Martijn van Calmthout, science communicator, writer and moderator. Eva Mendez (FAIRsFAIR), Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation), and Franciska de Jong (CLARIN ERIC, EOSC sustainability Working Group) provided the debate statements. The members of the debate teams were Joao Fernandes (ARCHIVER/CERN), Carole Goble (EOSC-Life), Mark Allen (ESCAPE), Daan Broeder (SSHOC), Ari Asmi (ENVRI-FAIR), Rudolf Dimper (PaNOSC), Stefano de Paoli (TRIPLE), Eetu Makela (FAIRsFAIR champion), Fotis Psomopoulos (CERTH, RDA ERC IG), Marialuisa Lavitrano (EOSC Association), Claudia Alén Amaro (EOSC-Life), Anca Hienola (ENVRI-FAIR), and Yannis Ioannidis (ESFRI).

The event consisted of three debates where two teams argued in favor or opposition of the statements. The event ended with a wrap up that summed the main points and final recommendations of the teams.

A total of 126 participants attended the debate. As the event took place within the RDA organisational framework, no information on the participants was collected.

Discussions: Key Points

The main points and recommendations of the debates were presented in the [official proceedings](#).¹³

Link to slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4723644>

Outcomes & Feedback

An official report detailing the final recommendations for the three topics was prepared after the event. The recommendations stress the needs for building a commons and for continued involvement of the researchers and end-users in the developments. Recommendations for improved governance were also suggested. An additional impact, suggested by debater Marc Allen in his post-event [blog post](#), was for the Science Clusters to learn from each other and build up a better understanding of the common challenges they face to make EOSC a reality.

¹³ Stephanie Parker, Ana Inkret, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Vasso Kalaitzi, Iris Buunk, & Jana Striova. (2021). The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5024589>

ANNEX 8

ROUND TABLE OF EXPERTS ON DATA CITATION

Event Report

Written by Nicolas Larrousse, CNRS

Background

The online [Round Table of Experts on Data Citation](#) was held on 20th May 2021 and was organized by SSHOC Task 3.4 in cooperation with SSHOC WP6. The round table aims to validate the work done in the Task 3.4 of SSHOC project and help refine the specifications of the FAIR SSH citation prototype, as well as inform Data Citation Recommendation both developed within the task. The content of the workshop was aligned with the SSHOC objective to promote Open science by addressing one of the crucial points in ensuring FAIR data. The workshop enabled participants to expand their knowledge about the importance of appropriate citation practices given by expert of the field coming from different institutions and organizations (UGOE, CLARIN, CNR/ISTI, CNRS, the Turing Institute, the Observatory of Paris - PSL Research University, Vienna - RDA data citation WG, OpenAIRE and CODATA).

Round Table Overview & Format

Aim. FAIR data are the pillar of Open Science which is at the core of the SSHOC project. In order to ensure findability of data and other resources, it is crucial to provide consistent data citation in the SSH domains. One of SSHOC's tasks (T 3.4) is dedicated to data citation and in particular making data citation machine actionable. This round table is a follow up of the discussions that began during a joint event, "[Realising the European Open Science Cloud](#)," between [SSHOC](#), [FREYA](#), and [EOSC-hub](#) in November 2020. This session was organized on data citation, where different approaches and experiences related to data citation were discussed by speakers from SSHOC and beyond.

After doing an inventory of SSH citation practices, the task is currently developing a prototype to implement what we called "FAIR SSH Data Citation" and based on that work drafted a first set of recommendations about data citation adapted to specific needs of SSH. For these discussions experts from known organizations like [RDA](#) and others will be invited.

Speakers. The panel of speakers was composed by:

- Alessia Bardi (OpenAire)
- Andreas Rauber (Vienna - RDA data citation WG)
- Barbara McGillivray (Turing Institute)
- Carlo-Maria Zwolf (Observatory of Paris - PSL Research University)
- Cesare Concordia (CNR/ISTI)
- Daan Broeder (CLARIN - SSHOC WP3 leader)
- Dieter Van Uytvanck (CLARIN)
- Jan Brase (UGOE)
- Nicolas Larrousse (Huma-Num CNRS)

- Simon Hodson (Executive Director of CODATA)

Organisers. The workshop was organised as a stand-alone online event in cooperation with partners in T6.5 and T3.4 of the SSHOC project.

Participation. There were 44 attendants of the round table. The majority of the participants came from European countries, mostly EU. The audience of the livestream covered stakeholder categories identified in D6.1. Almost all participants represented the scientific and research community (“Universities and Research Performing Institutions”, “Research and e-infrastructures”, “Research Libraries and Archives” and “Researchers, Research Networks and Communities”).

Brief summary of the event structure. The round table was organised as a virtual event due to the restrictions linked to Covid-19 pandemic. The round table lasted for one hour and thirty minutes and was divided into five parts: a short one dedicated to the presentation of the SSHOC project; a longer one where three main speakers presented on the topic of the workshop; and a hands-on session with discussion.

Presentations & Discussions: Key Points

First Session. Contextualisation

Speakers. Nicolas Larrousse (CNRS)

Main points. A brief contextual presentation by the speaker who also presented the Recommendations for FAIR Data Citation in the SHS. Indeed, he pointed out the reality that while there have been many initiatives to standardize data citation practices, there exist many communities of practice that have not yet harmonized.

Second Session. VAMDC, a world-renowned e-infrastructure for Astrophysics data and contextualization of the citation.

Speaker. Carlo Maria Zwolf (Observatory of Paris)

Main points. The speaker introduced the VAMDC, a world-renowned e-infrastructure for Astrophysics data. Even though VADMC provides a reliable mechanism to generate a citation (and therefore give credit to the author) it lacks the context of a citation, or put in another way, the intention behind a citation. For instance, it cannot evaluate the question: “was the citation made in a positive or negative way?” Understanding the intention behind a citation is crucial for scientific reasons. There is therefore a need to provide the community with the capacity to define the ‘role’ of cited data in a machine actionable way. This topic was presented during a Birds of a Feather (BoF) session during the 17th RDA plenary conference. The BoF then discussed what kind of annotation would be needed to express, in a machine-actionable way, the reason why A cites B.

The outcome is to create an RDA Interest Group to discuss this matter in more detail (e.g. granularity and curation of annotation).

Third Session. SSHOC Citation Service Prototype.

Speaker. Cesare Concordia (CNR/ISTI)

Main points. The speaker presented the Citation Service Prototype developed in the framework of task 3.4. The main goals are to:

- make SSH datasets citable;
- provide facilities for curation and semantic annotation of citations;
- visualise and exploit citations.

The speaker explained why we need to standardize and curate information to make it machine actionable, which can be done via the API component of the Citation Service Prototype.

The prototype was well-received by the round table, with several helpful suggestions being made for its future development.

Fourth Session. Question & Answers and general discussions

Speaker. All speakers

Main points. Following each presentation, the experts asked questions of the presenters and themselves, as well as sharing their experiences with data citation and their hopes for the future. These rich discussions gave rise the following points:

- Nowadays, identifying datasets with a PID is quite common, but descriptive metadata is still a problem.
- Data citation can happen at several levels, and that needs to be agreed upon before proceeding to avoid complications.
- Why are we citing? One of the most important reasons is for transparency, scrutiny, and the validation of one's scientific contribution. Doing so provides credit to the parties responsible for that data. A secondary effect is allowing data to be reused, and access should not be confused with citation.
- What is the goal of the citation? Is it quality assessment, recognition, or reference to the sources/reproducibility/interpretation analysis? These are not the same things, nor the same needs.
- Are we citing in a positive or a negative way? This information is not generally available.
- There is a need for a clear definition of what data in SSH is, as anything could be considered as data.
- Citations represent a particular moment in time, a snapshot.
- Semantic relationships are important.
- Quality has nothing to do with findability.
- The citation viewer could be useful to help researchers cite a data set properly.
- There is a difficulty in assessing the quality of data by a machine, therefore there is a need for human curation.
- The social role of a citation may be considered. For instance, "recognition with attribution" (for funders, colleagues etc.).
- Regarding standard recommendations for citations, a perfect standard doesn't exist.
- A lot of recommendations exist, as many working groups have focused on Data Citation, yet we still find ourselves in a situation with communities of practice but no concrete standards.
- Granularity of the citation is an open question; it suits some and doesn't suit others.
- The citation of dynamic data (e.g. from social networks) is a new challenge.
- There is a need for trusted infrastructures which provide different levels of services (e.g. OpenAire with <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>)

- Citation can be a good base for building data papers.
-

Fifth Session. Wrap up

Speaker. All speakers

Main points. Coming away from these presentations and rich discussions, we as a community need to reflect on why we cite: is it to provide evidence, to foster reuse, to give access, to give credit, or all these things combined?

It seems that the citation prototype developed in the context of the task is going in the right direction. In particular, the citation viewer was met with strong interest.

Outcomes & Feedback

Data citation is an important aspect of ensuring FAIR data, but it can often be challenging, which is why easy-to-use recommendations as well as discussion about possible issues and solutions are crucial.

All these remarks, suggestions and references made during the round table will be used to:

- Improve the citation prototype;
- Prepare the webinar planned for December;
- Feed into deliverable 3.5 and more generally into task 3.4 activities.

A possible output of this round table is the creation of a RDA Interest Group following the Bird of a Feather session - "Rich Metadata for annotation of citations contexts and data-citations contexts" - during the 17th RDA plenary.

ANNEX 9

ONBOARDING CITIZEN SCIENCE AND THE ROLE OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES: BARRIERS AND ACCELERATORS WORKSHOP REPORT

Written by Vasso Kalaitzi and Rosie Allison, LIBER

Background

This report concerns the SSHOC workshop [Onboarding Citizen Science and the role of research libraries: barriers and accelerators](#), which took place on June 23rd 2021 during the [LIBER 2021 Annual Conference](#). The session was co-organised by [SSHOC](#) and the [LIBER Citizen Science working group](#), with the contribution of prominent Citizen Science projects and initiatives, such as the [COESO project](#), the [University of Bordeaux](#) and the [INOS project](#), the [SDU Citizen Science Knowledge Centre](#), [Scientific Knowledge Services](#) and [COS4CLOUD](#). The workshop, as the LIBER2021 Conference, took place online, due to COVID19 pandemic restrictions, yet managed to fulfil its engagement goals thanks to engaging speakers and format, as well as its highly interesting and active audience. A blogpost on the workshop was published on the SSHOC website [here](#).

Workshop Overview & Format

The workshop built on the outcomes of the session "[Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?](#)" that took place during the conference "[Realising the European Open Science Cloud: Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond.](#)" in November 2020. Taking the results and questions from the previous session to a second level, the workshop aimed at raising awareness on the challenges and opportunities deriving from libraries' active involvement in Citizen Science in general, but also more specifically in relation to Social Sciences and Humanities. The role of the current workshop was to discuss how to advance SSH progress through participatory research with the help of the research libraries, by identifying barriers and accelerators. Synergies and collaborations will be discussed between the initiatives represented by the speakers and the participants and links between Citizen Science, SSHOC and the EOSC will be further explored.

The workshop devoted most of its duration to an interactive session with participants, where representatives of research libraries and/or archives (23), universities and/or research performing organisations (8), research and e-infrastructures (5) and private sector or industry players (4) actively contributed to the discussion by sharing their experience, expertise and ideas.

Presentations & Discussions: Key Points

Tatsiana Yankelevich, LIBER training coordinator, representing LIBER and SSHOC, chaired the session. She opened the session by providing some background information on the SSHOC project, its structure, goals and Key Exploitable results. Tatsiana walked the audience through previous collaborations between SSHOC and research libraries' and researchers, and outlined the format, structure and aims of the workshop.

Alessia Smaniotto, Project Manager, OpenEdition Center (EHESS), represented the COESO project, a framework for COllaborative EngagemenT on SOcietal issues, which builds on the Hypotheses.org platform. The project aims at contributing to overcoming the obstacles that hinder the development of Citizen Science in the SSH, facilitating and supporting participatory research in SSH, through a service-first approach. Ten Citizen Science pilots will represent a variety of disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens in different European countries. The project will also develop a Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation (VERA) and will collaborate with research funding organizations to enhance financial support to Citizen Science.

COESO will contribute to overcoming the obstacles that hinder the development of Citizen Science in the SSH, facilitating and supporting participatory research in SSH, through a service-first approach.

Ten Citizen Science pilots will represent a variety of disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens in different European countries. The first five pilots were provisioned since

the beginning of the project, while COESO aims to recruit the remaining five pilots through an open call at the end of 2021.

In the context of COESO, Citizen Science is understood as an umbrella term, covering earlier practices in the SSH, even when they have not been branded as “Citizen Science”. Citizen science is also about the researchers’ position/approach in working together with citizens towards solid and shareable knowledge. At the same time, strong connection with physical spaces and local professional communities is needed, and this is how libraries can also contribute, by building a sustainable environment with fluid transfer from digital to physical spaces.

The LIBER Citizen Science working group was represented by Thomas Kaarsted, Deputy Library Director, University Library of Southern Denmark. The working group is actively contributing to Citizen Science for research libraries in collaboration with other stakeholders, in terms of skills, digital templates and partnerships, among others. The LIBER Roadmap to Open Science makes a set of four strong recommendations to European research libraries, recommendations which remain as guidelines for the working group. Accordingly, the WG has agreed to the following strategic directions: 1. Projects, 2. Staff development, 3. Partnerships, 4. Advocacy, 5. Building infrastructure, 6. Research Librarians Guide. It was stressed that libraries can play a critical part in facilitating citizen science. In this context, the working group is developing [a Guide for Citizen Science for research libraries](#), as per the respective strategic direction.

WHAT CAN LIBRARIES CONTRIBUTE

FROM THE LIBER CITIZEN SCIENCE WORKING GROUP

Skills: Citizen Science skills development for staff, researchers, and the public

Infrastructures: As being active in the development of infrastructure for researchers to carry out Citizen Science

Good [open] scientific practice: as managing bodies around knowledge libraries that can translate good [Open Science] scholarly practice into new Citizen Science fields

Guidelines: develop guidelines for Citizen Science activities involving the library

The SDU Citizen Science Knowledge Centre was presented by Anne Kathrine Overgaard, Head of External Projects at the Faculty of Health Sciences at SDU and co-founder of SDU Citizen Science Knowledge Center, and it is a partnership between library and faculty, bridging public and policies, helping researchers in gathering better data through Citizen Science projects. Participation happens in 4 levels: Crowdsourcing, Distributed Intelligence, Participatory Science and Extreme. Three examples of Citizen Science projects were presented in this context: a) engaging local families to explore sustainable food (Humanities), b) exploring insect friendly areas and how willing people are to change their own gardens (Social sciences), c) loneliness in retired people, tackled by reading in groups (Humanities/health sciences).

The BESPOC model, a prototype for a single point of contact for Citizen Science, designed as a system of portals, frameworks, reports and connections, creating a digital desk to support the engagement of citizens, was presented by Tiberius Ignat, Director, Scientific Knowledge Services. Ultimate goal is to provide the tools building a community of curious minds that responds to the need for new ideas, broader geographical penetration, and more resources than funders can provide.

Hélène Schwalm, Projects officer, University of Bordeaux, presented the INOS project, an Erasmus+ project aiming at integrating Open and Citizen Science in active learning approaches in higher

education. It does so through connectivity & modernity, mixing participants and mentors, community building & pedagogical innovation & challenge-based learning. University of Bordeaux (UBx) participates in the project providing their expertise in open innovation activities. UBx is a large multidisciplinary university in “transition” working on 2 roadmaps (environmental and societal, open science). It is engaged in a global and participative reflection for 2030: modernising scientific mediation, creating intermediate spaces & acculturating to participation.

A position as an interface between science and society

- UBx is a large multidisciplinary university in « transition » : 2 roadmaps (environmental and societal, open science)
- An university engaged in a global and participative reflection for 2030:
 - Accompany the scientific mediation by modernizing it: scientists as referents (« manip confinées »)
 - Create some intermediate spaces, virtual or real to collect the citizens' needs: « Tiers lieu »,...
 - Acculturate to participation: participative budget,...

- Innovation Opportunities Office: design new programs that are relevant for the innovation ecosystem and pilot them with the academic staff, students, admin staff and partners
⇒ implies breaking down the university silos by connecting communities around these pilot programs.

Acculturate to open science and citizen science by experimenting new formats, notably open innovation activities

2

Angela Justamente Rodriguez, Communication Technician at CREAM, presented the COS4CLOUD project, which boosts Citizen Science technologies by building eleven user-centred services to be integrated in EOSC. Nine Citizen Science platforms are involved in the project to support sustainability and to increase the data quality and quantity, while the project implements co-designed sessions for the technological services and testing activities.

Cos4Cloud
Co-organizing Citizen Observations Experiences for the European Open Science Cloud

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 803463

What's your future perfect for citizen science engagement?

Create **user-friendly citizen science apps**. & try to avoid linguistic barriers by creating a citizen science app in diverse languages

Tools to **recognize citizens scientists' contribution to research**, for example, a notification informing the participant that her/his observation has been include in 'x' paper.

Include in the project budget to **hire specialized communication personnel** to create and work daily in the communication and engagement strategy.

Increase funding to increase citizen science projects' sustainability.

Increase the observations' credibility, so the academic, political, and social fields trust to use citizen science data.

Join efforts among various citizen science projects.

Organize joint activities (e.g., talks, workshops, promotion on social media, etc.) with **research libraries**.

The full programme and profiles of the speakers can be found [here](#). The presentations are available on Zenodo [here](#) and on YouTube [here](#).

Outcomes & Feedback

The workshop fulfilled its goal to discuss how to advance SSH progress through participatory research with the help of the research libraries, by identifying barriers and accelerators. Synergies and collaborations were discussed between the initiatives represented by the speakers and the participants and links between Citizen Science, SSHOC and the EOSC were further explored. A brainstorming session using the following [Google Jamboard](#) was moderated by Marieke Willems, Research Communication & Stakeholder Engagement, Trust-IT, on behalf of SSHOC. A series of boards were discussed with the audience, focussing on the following thematics:

- a) Board 1: Involving citizens in fostering scientific progress and open innovations. What are the barriers? What are the enablers? How can research libraries help?
- b) Board 2: Resources: What are the resources Citizen Science Researchers look for at your research library? How represented are SSH in the resources you suggest?
- c) Board 3: Recommendations for SSHOC: On how to foster the uptake of its SSH resources in Citizen Science; On how to link Citizen Science for scientific progress in the SSH to the wider EOSCecosystem.
- d) Board 4: Training & Skills. Have you identified any gaps in information or skills needed for Citizen Science, with SSH Researchers or Research Librarians? What type of advocacy, training and engagement would you say are needed to support Citizen Science in the SSH?

In the context of brainstorming with participants, speakers and organisers, a set of recommendations occurred around three areas:

1. Point of contact:
 - ★ To create guidance materials for stakeholders in the model of the upcoming Citizen Science for Research Libraries - A Guide;
 - ★ Show how existing resources and tools can be adapted for Citizen Science (e.g. complying with ethical aspects);
 - ★ Implement a BESPOC;
 - ★ Create connections between stakeholders and elements;
 - ★ Identify the end-users of the services.
2. Awareness raising
 - ★ Share SSH projects (results and activities) with other SSH researchers;
 - ★ Highlight the different names/branding of Citizen Science.
3. Linking to EOSC:
 - ★ Link to EOSC initiatives and highlight case studies to prove the added value and inclusiveness of Citizen Science.

ANNEX 10

ICTeSSH 2021 WORKSHOP: SSH VOCABULARY INITIATIVE - WHAT USERS WANT

Event Report

Written by Irena Vipavc Brvar, CESSDA/UL-ADP

Background

Upon a great success in delivering the workshop at ICTeSSH2020 on SSH Open Marketplace¹⁴ SSHOC decided to collaborate in the 2021 event as well. This gave partners great opportunity to present work done on vocabularies presented as self-standing events¹⁵ through the past year to a different community. This report concerns the workshop “SSH Vocabulary Initiative - What users want”¹⁶ that took place on 28th of June 2021, as pre-workshop to ICTeSSH conference.¹⁷ Event took place online and was free of charge. This event is part of the stakeholder series.

Workshop Overview & Format

SSHOC¹⁸ will build the Social Sciences and Humanities part of the European Open Science Cloud. One of the SSHOC project’s core objectives is to foster the transition from the current Social Sciences and Humanities landscape to a cloud-based infrastructure that will operate according to the FAIR principles, offering access to research data and related services adapted to the needs of the Social Science and Humanities (SSH) community.

The SSH European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) partnering in SSHOC are exploring and enabling collaboration and deeper integration of each other’s infrastructures. One topic that is of relevance for all SSHOC SSH stakeholders is that of managing and using vocabularies.

The SSH vocabularies are essential for a proper description of resources and phenomena and in SSHOC many tasks are concerned with them. In SSHOC, a specific “Vocabulary Initiative” was launched in 2020

¹⁴ Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: User Workshop.

<https://sshopencloud.eu/events/agile-development-ssh-open-marketplace-user-workshop> [8.10.2021]

¹⁵ WORKSHOP NOTES: SSHOC Requirements - Vocabularies and Vocabulary Management Platforms.

<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/workshop-notes-sshoc-requirements-vocabularies-and-vocabulary-management-platforms> [8.10.2021]

¹⁶ SSHOC Vocabulary Initiative - What users want (ICTeSSH 2021 SSHOC session).

<https://sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-vocabulary-initiative-what-users-want%C2%A0ictessh-2021-sshoc-session> [8.10.2021]

¹⁷ ICTeSSH - International Conference on ICT enhanced Social Sciences and Humanities 2021.

<http://testminis.uns.ac.rs/ictessh2021/> [8.10.2021]

¹⁸ Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud project. <https://sshopencloud.eu/> [8.10.2021]

to coordinate related vocabulary activities and investigate, inform and exchange expertise on vocabularies and the platforms that are hosting and managing them. Therefore, the workshop had the following main objectives:

- To engage the SSH end-user communities present at ICTeSSH in the SSHOC Vocabulary Initiative, to collect their input and feedback on managing vocabularies, and vocabularies as FAIR semantic artefacts.
- To raise awareness in the SSH research community present at ICTeSSH on finding, understanding and reusing vocabularies via the SSH Open Marketplace.

Workshop was organized and supported by SSHOC WP2 (Marieke Willems, TRUST-IT) and WP6 (Irena Vipavc Brvar, CESSDA/UL-ADP) with engagement of partners from WP3 and WP7 (Laure Barbot, DARIAH). SSH Vocabulary initiative was presented by Daan Broeder (CLARIN), which followed by covering user perspective, with Iulianna van der Lek (CLARIN) talking about different aspects of using vocabularies in the SSH community and the survey¹⁹ that was conducted on this topic. Further on Matej Ďurčo (DARIAH/OEAW) presented current ways of locating suitable vocabularies and using the SSH Open Marketplace²⁰, with which he covered the findability aspect. Interoperability aspects was covered with two presentations, first from Holly Wright (UoY-ADS) on The Vocabulary Matching Tool²¹, and second by Monica Monachini (CNR) on the usage of machine translations for creating multilingual vocabularies.

Event was one and a half hour long and consisted of main presentations and longer panel discussion with the engagements of participants. The panel consisted of all speakers and another expert on vocabularies Taina Jääskeläinen (CESSDA/TAU-FSD).

All participants were contacted in advance and were provided with questions that were used in the panel discussion so they could think and prepare their answers in advance. Reading materials was also provided:

- Controlled Vocabularies and SKOS at DARIAH campus²² include a short video on the same topic
- Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems²³
- SSHOC Takes Over @CLARINERIC Twitter Account²⁴ with #SSHOCaVocabulary #SSHOCifyCLARIN

153 people registered for the event, out of which 94 came from European countries (see Figure 1). Participants also came from 15 non-European countries, among which are United States (highest participation), but also India, Australia, Saudi Arabia and Nigeria.

¹⁹ Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Laure Barbot, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). SSHOC D7.6 Resources for Marketplace content description (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558339>

²⁰ SSH Open Marketplace. <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/> [8.10.2021]

²¹ Vocabulary Matching Tool. <https://heritagedata.org/vmt2/vmt-app.html> [8.10.2021]

²² Controlled Vocabularies and SKOS. <https://campus.dariah.eu/resource/controlled-vocabularies-and-skos> [8.10.2021]

²³ Broeder, Daan, Trippel, Thorsten, Degl'Innocenti, Emiliano, Giacomini, Roberta, Sanesi, Maurizio, Kleemola, Mari, Moilanen, Katja, Ala-Lahti, Henri, Jordan, Caspar, Alfredsson, Iris, L'Hours, Hervé, & Ďurčo, Matej. (2019). SSHOC D3.1 Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3569868>

²⁴ SSHOC Takes Over @CLARINERIC Twitter Account. <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-takes-over-clarineric-twitter-account> [8.10.2021]

52 people actually attended the event. By the end of September, when this report was written, 29 people viewed published recordings, and 58 viewed published slides.

The ICTeSSH 2021 online conference as a whole brought together 308 SSH researchers, computer scientists, informaticians, publishers, librarians, vendors of research ICT tools, and SSH decision-makers from 60 countries from all continents.

Figure 1: Registered participants per country (Europe exposed)

Some of the participants informed us about their role in their organization. Most of (see Figure 2). Most came from university environments (be it professors, researchers or IT support). Second larger group seems to be linked to libraries.

Figure 2: Participants were asked: What is your role in your organisation?

Participants were quite creative in proposing what kind of support they expect and what they would like to see further developed (see Figure 3). For more on this and other discussion points please see the official proceedings.

Figure 3: Participants were asked: What kind of support do you expect from research infrastructures / support services for vocabularies?

- Guidance on which vocabulary to use for a particular purpose. Quality, authority, sustainability. Backed by the community. Fit for purpose. Domain relevance. Machine access.
- Ease of access, guidance on which vocabulary to use and support in terms of mapping
- Hosting a mapping tool
- to put a quality stamp to a certain vocabulary
- Support for as many vocabularies as feasible, crosswalks.
- Registries and vocabs
- services like mapping
- I expect them to hide all interoperability complexity
- advice how to create vocabs
- Ease of access.
- Suitable repos
- Technical, advisory support

Agenda

Time	Title	Speaker
9.00-9.10	The SSH-SSHOC Vocabulary Initiative	Daan Broeder (CLARIN)
9.10-9.40	<p><i>How can researchers use Vocabulary in SSH tools & use cases</i></p> <p>USABILITY: Using Vocabularies in the SSH community (Iulianna van der Lek, CLARIN)</p> <p>FINDABILITY: Current ways of locating suitable vocabularies (Matej Ďurčo, DARIAH/OEAW)</p> <p>INTEROPERABILITY: Vocabulary Matching Tool (Holly Wright, UoY-ADS) 5 min</p> <p>INTEROPERABILITY: Use of MT for creating multilingual vocabularies Monica Monachini (CNR)</p>	Moderator: Marieke Willems (Trust-IT)
9.40-10.25	<p>Slid.do with the audience & panel discussion</p> <p>SSH Vocabulary Initiative - What users want</p> <p>Panellists:</p>	Moderator: Marieke Willems (Trust-IT)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daan Broeder (CLARIN) • Iulianna van der Lek (CLARIN) • Holly Wright (UoY-ADS) • Monica Monachini (CNR) • Matej Ďurčo (DARIAH/OEAW) • Taina Jääskeläinen (CESSDA/TAU-FSD) 	
10.25-10.30	Wrap up	Daan Broeder (CLARIN)

Presentations & Discussions: Key Points

The main points of the presentations and discussion were summarized in the official proceedings.²⁵ Slides²⁶ and video recording²⁷ of the event are also available.

Outcomes & Feedback

Participants were asked to provide feedback on the event. Among those few who did, the majority answered that they would rate the event with top grade and they were very satisfied with organizational aspects. Participants ranked from beginners to the experts, when some pointed out that they received diverse information and will follow on them, and others have already concrete ideas how they will use what was presented (see Figure 4 and 5).

Figure 4: Participants were asked: What did you hope to gain from the workshop?

work on further with the input gained
Contents and ideas
A new orientation in research enquiry and implementation
See how SSHOC approaches community consultation & update
knowledge
Though I joined in late due to internet hitches, I gained perspectives on the apt usage of vocabularies to suit different context.

²⁵ Barbot, L., Broeder, D., Durco, M., Jääskeläinen, T., Lek, I. van der, Monachini, M., ... Wright, H. (2021). SSH Vocabulary Initiative - What users want. In *Proceedings of the ICTeSSH 2021 conference*.
<https://doi.org/10.21428/7a45813f.ca4aecfc>

²⁶ Broeder, Daan, van der Lek, Iulianna, Monachi, Monica, Wright, Holly, Jääskeläinen, Taina, Durco, Matej, & Willems, Marieke. (2021, June 30). SSH Vocabulary Initiative - What Users Want. ICTeSSH2021, online. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5045017>

²⁷ Workshop: SSHOC Vocabulary Initiative - What Users Want. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NSHl2fr4Uzs> [8.10.2021]

Figure 5: Participants were asked: Do you see this workshop having a positive impact on your work and how?

will try to do some research on vocab.
Great
Definitely, it would have a great impact. Help reshape my approach to research
Better understanding of some of the issues arising & approaches taken
yes, additional material
I see it having a positive impact on my work because it had availed an opportunity for me to learn and research further of mapping.

Participants mentioned that they liked the pace and apt delivery of the event. A participant even suggested the event could be longer with further treatment of the topics at hand. They pointed out that they were able to join due to the fact that the event was delivered online. There was one comment on possible improvement of the audio of speakers. Unfortunately, this is one element organizing partners were not able to control. It is easier to control hardware and network when you deliver events in person, but mostly impossible online. Due to elements like this, moderation and technical support is especially challenging.

The workshop reviewed the uses and needs with respect to vocabularies in the SSH. The main outcomes from the audience participation and discussion, important for SSHOC work in the SSH Vocabulary Initiative are:

1. The appreciation and desire for multilingual vocabularies.
2. Mention of the biomed example for vocabulary registration, e.g. Bioportal and the generic version Ontoport.
3. The non-technical issues pertaining to vocabulary management/curation of social (involvement) and economic (funding) nature.
4. The importance of the provider when a researcher assesses the quality of vocabularies.